

**KNOWLEDGE OF HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS AND FACILITY READINESS
FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF PERINATAL ASPHYXIA IN HEALTH
FACILITIES IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

This chapter offers a general background to this study. It presents and describes the research problems, objectives of the research and the significance of the study. In addition, it provides operational definition of concepts used, as well as limitations and delimitations of the study.

1.1 Background to the Study

The transition from fetal to extra-uterine life is accompanied by a series of unique physiological events and processes that ensure that the newborn adapts to extra-uterine life successfully (Perry *et al.*, 2014). Weiner (2016) noted that during labour, the umbilical cord contracts and is compressed, thereby leading to a hike in carbon dioxide and a fall in oxygen concentrations in the fetal blood. These cause the oxygen supply to vital organs in the newborn to be reduced as a result of alteration in pulmonary gas exchange, culminating in hypoxemia and hypercarbia (Tasew *et al.*, 2018). The oxygenation of the fetal blood is often compromised by the complexity of this labour process (Perry *et al.*, 2014). Nonetheless, Rakel and Rakel (2016) observed that a healthy, strong and vigorous newborn that is breathing and cries with a strong respiratory effort will transit through the respiratory phase independently with no complications.

Over the last decade, under-five mortality has witnessed a downward trend, conversely, neonatal mortality is yet to keep pace with this significant improvement (Narayanan, 2016). Globally, it has been estimated that about 2.7 million newborns die each year, largely as a result of perinatal asphyxia, complications of preterm birth

and infections. Sub-Saharan Africa has the highest neonatal mortality rates (NMRs), experiencing a mortality reduction of 28% since 1990 (Graft-johnson *et al.*, 2017a).

Perinatal asphyxia is one of the most prominent causes of neonatal deaths in the world as it has been estimated that 25% of approximately 4 million neonatal deaths worldwide are secondary to birth asphyxia (Vali, Mathew & Lakshminrusimha, 2015).

This condition is the failure of a newborn to initiate and sustain breathing at birth (World Health Organization, 2014). Tasew *et al.* (2018) also defined asphyxia as impairment in placental or pulmonary gas exchange that leads to hypoxemia and hypercarbia. Similarly, Fattuoni, Palmas, Noto, Fanos and Barberini, (2015), defined perinatal asphyxia as an oxygen deprivation that occurs around the time of birth. However, Rakel and Rakel (2016) observed that a healthy, strong and vigorous newborn that is breathing and cries with a strong respiratory effort will transit through the respiratory phase independently with no complications. Narayanan (2016) estimated that about 5-10 percent of newborns will require this extra assistance at birth.

According to World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, around 3% of approximately 120 million infants born every year in developing countries develop perinatal asphyxia.

Failure to initiate interventions for a newborn with asphyxia could lead to death or severe neurological sequelae. The burden of neonatal deaths due to asphyxia is disproportionately concentrated in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs). It is estimated that some 900,000 of these newborns die each year. However, in a study by Hoque (2017), it was posited that the high incidence of

morbidity and mortality that results from perinatal asphyxia can be reduced through effective management of the condition.

Although the need for the management of PA may be anticipated, there are many occasions when it is unexpected. For instance, Tecla, Franklin, David and Jackson (2017) noted that some maternal conditions have been identified to be predisposing factors for asphyxia in a newborn, some of which are eclampsia, diabetes, hypertension in pregnancy, prolonged labour, among others. Also, Gebreheat et al., (2018), in their own study pointed that instrumental delivery, cesarean birth, prolonged labour, early rupture of membrane, maternal fever, anaemia and meconium stained liquor were significantly associated with perinatal asphyxia. While approximately 85 percent of births require no intervention to initiate spontaneous breaths, about 10 percent of newborns will need minimal interventions; a further 3 percent will require positive pressure respiratory support and another 2 percent will need to be intubated to augment their respiratory efforts (Ndzima-Konzeka, 2017).

The full range of resuscitation interventions will be required by 0.1% of newborns (Shikuku et al., 2018). Aliyu, Lawal and Onankpa (2017) thus posited that if resuscitation is not done in a timely and effective manner, it will lead to death or irreversible damage of some vital organs in the newborn. Many newborns that require resuscitation have no identifiable risk factors before birth. Therefore, management of asphyxia which includes basic resuscitation must be anticipated at every birth, and preparation must be made.

As part of the interventions to reduce the prevalence, morbidity and mortality due to perinatal asphyxia, the World Health Organization (WHO) and American Heart

Association recommend that every birth should be attended by at least one healthcare provider who is able to initiate newborn resuscitation (Simpson & Creehan, 2014; World Health Organization, 2017). These healthcare providers are otherwise called skilled birth attendants. Similarly, as part of health facility readiness for the management of asphyxia, WHO advocates that essential equipment like bag and mask for resuscitation, mucus extractor for suctioning, source of warmth for thermal protection, a clock and a good source of light must be present in the labour room for basic resuscitation (Danilel Muturi Gichogo, 2016).

The management of PA consists of an array of services provided by healthcare providers to ensure that the airway of an asphyxiated newborn remains clear and unimpeded and breathing, spontaneous and unassisted, such that there will be adequate circulation to perfuse the tissues and organs of the newborn (Simpson & Creehan, 2014). One major component of perinatal asphyxia management is resuscitation, which according to Oloyede and Udo (2016) was defined as airway clearing (suctioning if required), head positioning and positive pressure ventilation via bag and mask.

However, some healthcare providers are either not prepared due to lack of training and skill or do not have enough resources in their health facilities to manage asphyxiated newborns effectively. Egharevba, Kayode-Adedeji, and Alikah (2018) in their study on perinatal asphyxia in a rural Nigerian hospital observed that less than 20 per cent of health facilities in Nigeria offer emergency obstetric care, and only 35 per cent of deliveries are attended by skilled birth attendants. Moreover, the distribution of existing health facilities is inequitable as there is concentration in

urban areas, of which only about 35% of the Nigerian population can access (Abhulimhen-iyoha et al., 2016). Thus, in some cases, even when one travels several kilometers to access health care, the possibility of getting quality service is not guaranteed because most health facilities are not prepared for quality service delivery due to inadequacy of human and material resources. There is therefore a necessity to assess the knowledge of healthcare providers and facility readiness for the management of PA across the three levels of health facilities in Osun State.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Globally, the rate of mortality among the under-five children has witnessed a downward trend in the past decade from about 11.9 million to about 5.9 million (Sami *et al.*, 2017). However, neonatal mortality rate is yet to keep abreast with this improvement and far from meeting SDG4, especially in developing countries (Ezenduka *et al.*, 2016) where 45% of all under-five deaths occur during the neonatal period (Gebreheat *et al.*, 2018). Nigeria has the highest absolute number of annual newborn deaths among countries in Africa, accounting for 255,500 of the 912,000 newborn deaths (Graft-johnson *et al.*, 2017a). With a neonatal mortality rate of 48/1000 live births, and over 700 newborn deaths each day, Nigeria has the highest number of newborn deaths in Sub Sahara Africa and contributes about 8% of the total world's neonatal deaths (Ezenduka et al., 2016). As posited by Aliyu *et al.* (2017), the three leading causes of neonatal death include perinatal asphyxia, infection and prematurity, with perinatal asphyxia accounting for one-quarter of all neonatal deaths across the globe, 23% of all neonatal deaths in low-income countries (Gebreheat *et al.*, 2018) and 26 per 1000 live births in Nigeria (Egharevba

et al., 2018).

Although, it has been proven that prompt management of asphyxia is effective for the prevention of deaths due to the condition, a number of health facilities in developing countries are grossly deficient in equipment, human resource, drugs and other supplies that are essential for managing perinatal asphyxia (Oloyede & Udo, 2016), while some others suffer a dearth of human resources in this regard (Jukkala & Henly, 2009; Kalaniti & Schm, 2015). Thus, a large percentage of deaths and complications that are recorded during the neonatal period have been noted to be associated with inadequacy of human and material resources in health facilities for birth and the management of asphyxia (Johnson, 2018a; Trevisanuto et al., 2016).

The consequences of non-readiness of facilities for the management of asphyxia may be overly inestimable because the condition is associated with long term sequelae which results in a global burden of 42 million disability-adjusted years (Aliyu et al., 2017). Similarly, the complications that arise from an improperly managed perinatal asphyxia span considerable morbidity, long-term disability (including cerebral palsy, epilepsy and sensory deficits) and mortality among this age group (Nair & Kumar, 2018). These portend a negative effect on the economy, productivity and development of the affected baby, families, communities and the nation in its entirety.

Despite the fact that much has been written on perinatal asphyxia management globally and nationally, there remains a dearth of information on facility readiness for this service in this part of the world (Johnson, 2018b). To date, little research has been conducted in Nigeria to evaluate facility readiness related factors that are

necessary for reducing the prevalence of and deaths that occur due to perinatal asphyxia. Most of the studies that have been carried out on perinatal asphyxia in Nigeria have evaluated the prevalence and risk factors associated with the menace (Egharevba *et al.*, 2018; Exley *et al.*, 2018; Ezenduka *et al.*, 2016). Few studies have been done to evaluate the level of readiness of health facilities in terms of appropriate structure, periodic staff training, guidelines on the management of asphyxia as well as adequate supply of basic medications and equipment (in functioning conditions), all of which are pertinent to drastically reducing the rate of newborn mortality so that Nigeria can keep pace with the recommended sustainable development goal four (SDG4).

This study therefore assessed the knowledge of healthcare providers and the readiness of health facilities in Osun State for the management of PA as a prerequisite for improving survival and reducing the burden associated with this condition in the newborn.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in health facilities in Osun State?
2. What is the level of knowledge of perinatal asphyxia management among healthcare providers in selected health facilities in Osun state?
3. What is the extent of facility readiness for the management of PA in health facilities in Osun State?
4. What are the barriers to facility readiness for perinatal asphyxia management in selected health facilities in Osun State?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. estimate the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in health facilities Osun state;
2. assess the knowledge of perinatal asphyxia management among healthcare providers in selected health facilities in Osun State;
3. assess facility readiness for the management of PA in selected health facilities in Osun State; and
4. explore the barriers to the management of PA in selected health facilities in Osun State.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study focused on the assessment of the knowledge of healthcare providers, specifically those working in the delivery room and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) on the basic requirement for the management of PA at different facility levels. An assessment of the knowledge of healthcare providers on perinatal asphyxia management may provide an impetus for introduction of in-service training for healthcare providers in specific areas of deficit. This may further provide a guide for pre-service training for upcoming caregivers in order to reinforce knowledge, improve competence, increase the level of confidence and promote positive attitudes towards the management of PA.

The assessment of facility readiness for the management of PA provides empirical evidence that may substantiate the need for strategic planning in resource provision and allocation that may contribute to the reduction of the rate of newborn deaths associated with perinatal asphyxia. The findings from availability of guidelines and protocols on the management of PA may be useful in evaluation of the

implementation of national health policies on newborn care at different facility levels. Similarly, the findings may guide the management of different facilities in making policies and improving the supply of resources (personnel, equipment and medications) that are basically required for the facilities to offer effective services that are indispensable for the management of newborns with asphyxia. The study may also enlighten the government to prioritize the allocation of resources based on delivery load per health facility, especially in relation to attaining SDG 4.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

The components that were assessed during the study are service availability and readiness for the management of PA and the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in health facilities in Osun State. However, during the course of the study, some limitations were encountered. The study was envisaged to be susceptible to a high rate of attrition because of acute short staffing that was reported to be due to healthcare providers dropping out of service, retiring, geographical relocation of participants due to transfer from current unit with no replacement. This was handled by consecutively recruiting all healthcare providers working in those areas of chronic shortage in the knowledge assessment section of the study.

Similarly, the study was done across three levels of health facilities by government and no private health facility was included. Therefore, caution should be taken regarding the interpretation of perinatal asphyxia in Osun State.

This study only assessed the knowledge component of healthcare providers in the management of PA, assessment of skills was not conducted. This was due to non-availability of mannequins to simulate the procedure which would have helped in the

assessment of the skills, confidence and competence of healthcare providers in the management of PA through direct observation.

1.7 Delimitation of the Study

The study will be delimited to government owned health facilities in Osun state.

1.8 Operational Definition of Terms

Asphyxia: inability or failure of a newborn to initiate and sustain breathing at birth

Attitude: perceived abilities of healthcare providers that is dependent on basic training

Health Facilities: health centers and hospitals that are owned and managed by the government.

Readiness: this is the ability of health facilities to offer services for the management of PA. This term will be used synonymously with preparedness in this study.

Healthcare Providers: this will include medical doctors, nurses, and community health practitioners that attend to deliveries in the selected health facilities.

Health workforce density: core medical professionals per 10 000 population; physicians, non-physician clinicians, registered nurses, and midwives. This includes part-time physicians who are given the value of 0.5 in the scoring.

Maternity ward: this refers to a single unit where the labour room (first stage and second stage) and post natal wards have been merged into a single unit under the management of a single set of healthcare providers as obtainable in primary and secondary facilities in this study setting.

Skilled Health Attendants: nurses and doctors that take deliveries in the selected facilities.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This review of literature described existing evidence for healthcare providers knowledge and facility readiness for the management of PA. The review was done to explore the link between facility readiness and the knowledge of healthcare providers as well as the barrier to the management of PA.

2.1 Overview of Perinatal Asphyxia

Neonatal mortality indicator plays an important role in providing the required information needed to improve the health status of pregnant women, new mothers and newborn, allowing decision makers to identify problems, tackle temporal and geographical trend and access changes in policy and practice. This is one of the most important vital statistics that is used to measure how well a nation is fairing in terms of maternal and fetal outcome (Wise, 2017). However, neonatal mortality continues to be a public health problem despite many years of research design to identify its risk factors. Neonatal mortality in the 2013 national demographic and health survey (NDHS) was highest amongst teenage mothers and mothers aged 40-49 (55/1000, 65/1000) respectively and lowest in urban residence (34/1000) (Osuji, & Nwosu, 2015).

Perinatal mortality has been defined by World Health Organization (WHO) (2014) as the number of stillbirths and deaths per 1000 total live births that occur within the first seven days of life. Furthermore, (Khupakonke et al., 2017) described as

perinatal mortality as deaths in the first week of life including still births, and also submitted that it is at an unacceptably high level in developing countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa (Khupakonke et al., 2017). The estimated incidences of perinatal deaths vary worldwide based on socio-economic, demographic and clinical profiles. Recent estimates show that the perinatal mortality rate (PNMR) in developed regions of the world is about 10 per 1000 live births compared with more than 50 per 1000 live births in less developed regions of the world (Debillon et al., 2018). Globally, the perinatal mortality rate fell from 33 per 1,000 live births in 1990 to 20 per 1,000 in 2013. Sub-Saharan Africa has lagged behind other regions with the highest neonatal mortality rate of 31 deaths per 1,000 live births (Kamau, 2018). In developing countries however, mortality is still unacceptably high, ranging from 4.6 per 1000 in Cape Town, South Africa to 26 per 1000 in Nigeria.

Globally, Nigeria ranks second to India with the highest number of neonatal deaths, as well as the highest reported number in Africa (Ezeh, Agho, Dibley, Hall, & Page, 2014). These authors reiterated in their study on the causes of neonatal mortality in Nigeria that each year, more than a quarter million neonates die, which translates to approximately 700 neonates every day. Perinatal mortality remains disturbingly high in Nigeria despite the significant decline in most parts of the developing world, including some sub-Sahara African countries, such as Ghana and Uganda. A recent United Nations (UN) report on childhood mortality reported that over the last 2 decades, the Nigerian neonatal mortality rate (NMR) dropped by only 20.4%, from 49 deaths per 1000 live births in 1990 to 39 in 2011. Similarly, evidence from the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) also indicated a marginal decline of 4.8%

(42 deaths per 1000 live births in 1990 to 40 in 2008). The 39 and 40 neonatal deaths per 1000 live births reported by the UN and NDHS, respectively, can be interpreted as approximately one in every 25 neonates born in Nigeria died in the first month of life.

One of the most important causes of morbidity and mortality around the perinatal period is asphyxia (Gebreheat et al., 2018b). According to the same author, perinatal asphyxia is defined as the failure of a newborn to initiate and sustain spontaneous respiration at birth (World Health Organization (WHO, 2016). Similarly, asphyxia was described by Ezenduka, Ndie, & Oburoh, (2016) to refer to the failure of the newborn to establish and sustain respiration at one minute of life. This definition was corroborated by Hoque, 2017, who defined asphyxia as a condition of the fetus or newborn that is due to failure to breath or breathing poorly leading to decrease oxygen perfusion to various organs. It will be noted that all the definitions above focus on a central theme, lack or insufficient supply of oxygen. The characteristics of this condition include impairment in respiratory gases exchange, culminating in hypoxemia and hypercapnia that is usually accompanied by metabolic acidosis (Gobezie et al., 2019).

2.5 Management of Perinatal Asphyxia.

At least 90 % of newborns make the transition from intrauterine to extra uterine life without difficulty (AHA/AAP, 2016). Some newborns on the other hand may fail to initiate and sustain spontaneous breathing. Consequently, they become oxygen deprived. There are circulatory and non-circulatory adaptive mechanisms that exist,

allowing the newborn to cope with asphyxia and preserve vital organ function of the adrenal gland, heart, and brain. Nevertheless, these compensatory mechanisms fail in the presence of severe and/or prolonged insults, resulting in hypoxic ischemic injury which leads to cell death via necrosis and apoptosis (Rainaldi & Perlman 2016). A newborn experiencing difficulty in this transition requires timely and effective management through active resuscitation measures with (or without) the administration of selected medications.

The ability of the healthcare providers to assess and diagnose a newborn with perinatal is the first right step on the track of managing perinatal asphyxia. In a policy statement by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists and American Academy of Pediatrics, Martin et al., (2006) submitted that the APGAR score serves as a tool for determining the physiologic status of a newborn immediately after birth. Its unilateral requirement for the diagnosis of perinatal asphyxia has become unacceptable because of the elements of the score are dependent on the physiologic maturity of the infant, and is often influenced by other factors like drugs, preterm birth, congenital anomalies and infection (Chiabi et al., 2019). The authors subsequently concluded that the use of APGAR score to ascertain the diagnosis of asphyxia is inappropriate but should rather be limited to the assessment of the newborn during the immediate post-partum period (Chiabi et al., 2019; Martin et al., 2006).

Contrary to this submission, in most of the settings where perinatal asphyxia is predominant, the luxury of resources to perform the complex laboratory investigations to confirm the diagnosis are grossly deficient (Wagner, 2015), thus

the healthcare providers have been restricted to the use of APGAR score as the only evidence that a newborn is asphyxiated. Therefore, several studies in these settings have it documented that a diagnosis of mild, moderate and severe asphyxia can be made when the APGAR score ≤ 7 , ≤ 6 and ≤ 3 in the first 1 and 5 minutes of life respectively.

The management of PA depends on the severity of the condition and the extent of neurological damage. Effective management involves provision of timely and essential interventions including diagnosis of the condition, provision of warmth, drying and rubbing, stimulation to breathe, clearing the airway, active ventilating with bag and mask(basic resuscitation), advanced resuscitation (including intubation and use of medications) if necessary, in order to prevent complications that may arise from tissue damage following delay in response to asphyxia (Callister, 2016; Graft-johnson et al., 2017). According to Weiner, (2016), the most important goal of immediate management of an asphyxiated newborn is to ventilate the lungs of the of the newborn baby.

Newborn stimulation is a technology-free practice that includes drying and rubbing has been documented to be helpful in initiating breathing in asphyxiated newborns (Graft-johnson et al., 2017). This can be maximally achieved by taking advantage of the golden moment (the first minute following birth) in order to reduce the rate of asphyxia in newborn babies (Callister, 2016). Graft-johnson et al. further submitted that across the globe, approximately 10 million babies will require stimulation to initiate breathing every year. Therefore, it is essential that healthcare providers attending to birth should acquire and perform this skill adequately when required.

Resuscitation of a newborn requires a graded response for those that are not making transition effectively (Weiner, 2016). This may involve positive pressure ventilation with bag and mask, chest compressions and rarely medications (AAP, 2011). Globally, about 6 million babies will require basic resuscitation annually (Graft-johnson et al., 2017). The airway, breathing and circulation (ABC) approach is applied in newborn resuscitation. Airway is assessed for secretions or meconium and cleared if any (Weiner, 2016). Once the airway is clear the baby is dried and stimulated by rubbing the back once or twice or flicking the soles of the feet and then placed in neutral position (Weiner, 2016).

The step on breathing includes assessing if it is absent, poor or checking for gasping respirations. If any of these is present, the birth attendant should call for help and initiate ventilation with bag and mask at a rate of 30 breaths per minute. Breathing should be started within 60sec of life, this is called the 'golden minute'. For asphyxiated term newborn babies, it is recommended that room air should be used for initial resuscitation because evidence has shown that these neonates achieve higher Apgar scores and heart rates within 5mins and 90 seconds of age respectively (Sussman & Weiss, 2013). Graft-johnson et al. supported this opinion by stating that ventilation with room air have a positive impact on the survival of asphyxiated infants and further emphasized that this can be achieved basic training of healthcare providers. On the average, the amount of pressure required in a term baby is 30cm water for 2-3 sec in order to aerate the lungs. Pre-term babies may require less pressure of about 20-25 cm water (Resuscitation Council, 2010). Some of the respiratory changes occurring as a result of successful transition into extra

uterine life include patent alveoli with establishment of spontaneous breathing (Kamau, 2018).

With effective ventilation the heart rate increases to more than 100 beats per minute. Once this is accomplished and the airway secured, the resuscitation team should avoid hyperthermia of the newborn by turning off the radiant warmer so that passive cooling can be achieved (Sussman & Weiss, 2013). Circulation is supported by starting chest compressions if the heart rate is below 60 beats per minute. For every one effective breath, three chest compressions are administered for the duration of one minute. The ABC is reassessed every 1-2 minutes until heart rate is above 60 beats per minute and the breathing is adequate (Weiner, 2016).

There is a significant difference in the management of mild asphyxia and moderate/severe asphyxia. According to the standard treatment protocol for the management of common newborn conditions that was adapted from WHO guidelines, in addition to the stimulation, rubbing and the provision of warmth, a newborn with mild asphyxia will also require bag and mask ventilation (BMV) for about 60 seconds in order to initiate and sustain breathing (<http://www.newbornwhocc.org/>). However, a newborn with moderate/severe asphyxia will require BMV for more than 60 seconds as well as the need for intubation, with (or without) medications. Similarly, a moderately/severely asphyxiated newborn will require a close monitoring of vitals like the temperature, heart rate (HR), capillary refill time (CRT), colour, oxygen saturation (SpO₂), respiratory rate (RR), lower chest retractions and abnormal movements (like seizures). This will be done for a period of about 72 hours while the neonate is still in

the hospital in order to prevent further complications.

One of the effective measures to prevent the deaths due to neonatal asphyxia is to have birth attendants that are skilled in neonatal resuscitation. In one of the studies done to assess the intervention that can be undertaken to reduce deaths from birth asphyxia, neonatal resuscitation was found to be a highly effective intervention (Kamau, 2018). According to Lee et al., (2011), neonatal resuscitation is defined as the set of interventions at the time of birth to support the establishment of breathing and circulation, whereas, intervention after a baby is born to help it breathe and to help its heart beat. Wyckoff et al., (2015) in a guideline designed by the American heart association affirmed that neonatal resuscitation applies primarily to newly born infants transitioning from intrauterine to extra-uterine life. The recommendations are also applicable to neonates who have completed newborn transition and require resuscitation during the first weeks after birth. The goals of neonatal resuscitation are to prevent the morbidity and mortality associated with hypoxic ischaemic tissue (brain, heart, and kidney) injury and also to re-establish adequate spontaneous respiration and cardiac output.

Figure 2.1: Management of Perinatal Asphyxia (World Health Organization (WHO), 2014)

Figure 2.2: Management of Perinatal Asphyxia (World Health Organization (WHO), 2014)

Figure 2.3: Neonatal Resuscitation Algorithm (Wyckoff et al., 2015)

Equipment and Supplies for the Management of Perinatal Aphyxia

Requisite for effective neonatal care immediately after delivery are the availability of basic resuscitation devices for perinatal asphyxia, adequate number of skilled birth attendants and infrastructure in order to achieve a reduction in morbidity resulting from neonatal asphyxia (Tecla, Franklin, David, & Jackson, 2018). According to WHO (2016), life saving commodities that were recommended for the resuscitation of a newborn with asphyxia include self-inflating neonatal resuscitation bag with masks (size 0 for pre-term and size 1 for term babies), electric operated suction machine or pump, suction catheter (of about 50cm length), single use suction bulb or multi-use suction bulb that can be opened, cleaned and sterilized, training mannequin for neonatal resuscitation and infant stethoscope. In another study, Rakel and Rakel, (2016) identified the supplies and equipment for the resuscitation of a term infant to include: suction equipment- bulb syringe, mechanical suction and tubing, suction catheters, 8-Fr feeding tube and 20-nL syringe, meconium aspirator; bag and mask equipment- neonatal resuscitation bag with pressure release valve or pressure manometer, face masks (newborn and premature sizes), oxygen source with flow meter and tubing; medications- epinephrine 1:10,000, isotonic crystalloid for volume expansion, sodium bicarbonate 4.2%, naloxone hydrochloride

The comprehensive list of basic and advanced neonatal resuscitation supplies and equipment for the management of PA as provided by Weiner (2016) in the textbook of neonatal resuscitation include:

Suction equipment: Bulb syringe, mechanical suction and tubing, suction catheters, and meconium aspirator.

Positive-pressure ventilation equipment: Device for delivering positive-pressure ventilation, face masks (newborn and preterm sizes), oxygen source, compressed air source, oxygen blender to mix oxygen and compressed air with flow meter, (flow rate set to 10 L/min) and tubing, pulse oximeter with sensor and cover, and target oxygen saturation table.

Warmth: Preheated warmer, warm towels or blankets, temperature sensor and sensor cover for prolonged resuscitation, hat, plastic bag or plastic wrap (<32 weeks' gestation), and thermal mattress (<32 weeks' gestation).

Oxygenate: equipment to give free-flow oxygen, pulse oximeter with sensor and cover, and target oxygen saturation table.

Ventilate: Flowmeter set to 10 Umin, oxygen blender set to 21 % (21 %-30% if <35 weeks' gestation), positive-pressure ventilation (PPV) device, term- and preterm-sized masks, 8F feeding tube and large syringe.

Intubation equipment: Laryngoscope with straight blades (No. 0 for preterm babies and No. 1 for term babies), extra bulbs and batteries for laryngoscope, endotracheal tubes (2.5-, 3.0-, 3.5-mm internal diameter (ID)), and stylet (optional).

Medications: Epinephrine 1:10,000 (0.1 mg/mL)- 3-mL or 10-mL ampoules, normal saline for volume expansion-100 or 250 mL, dextrose 10%, 250 mL (optional), normal saline for flushes, and syringes (1-mL, 3-mL or 5-mL, 20- to 60-mL).

The author above however did not include the availability of safe water and source of power as requisite for some of the appliances listed above to function. In the absence of continuous supply of running water and other resources like reliable supply of electricity, effective communication system, round the clock maternal and

neonatal care services, evidenced based clinical guidelines and protocols, technical support and supervision, and regular supply of drugs and basic equipment, it will be difficult for the healthcare provider to carry out NR effectively (Tecla et al., 2018).

A resuscitation trolley is useful but is not absolutely necessary. In the operating theatre where caesarean sections are performed, a corner that is protected from draught and can be kept warm should be prepared for the immediate care of the newborn, including resuscitation when needed. An institution should have at least two sets of equipment in case of multiple births, or for other births occurring at the same time, or in case one set does not function (Allen et al., 2017).

In resource poor countries, it has been proven that the availability of ambu bag and mask is sufficient to yield a high-impact intervention which is necessary to reduce mortality due to birth asphyxia in these regions (Kim et al., 2013). Bag and mask have been included by the United Nations Commission on Life-Saving Commodities for Women and Children as part of the list of affordable, effective and life-saving tools for newborn resuscitation, but they are often underutilized by healthcare providers in low resource countries (Kim et al., 2013).

Complications of Asphyxia and Sequelae

Some serious neonatal complications notable among the asphyxiated babies as identified by Hoque, (2017) are hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy with convulsion, neonatal jaundice, septicemia, transient tachypnoea of neonate, hypoglycemia, respiratory distress syndrome, caput succedaneum and feeding problem. A major complication in the brain includes hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy .Other affected organs include gut, kidneys, skin and severe hypoxic ischaemic injury can

result in multi organ failure and consequently death (Kamau, 2018).

In severe cases of birth asphyxia, other long term complications have been noted such as neurodegenerative diseases, mental retardation and epilepsy. Mild insults are characterized by minimal brain damage disorders such as attention deficit and hyperactivity (Shikuku et al., 2018). The main goal of resuscitation is therefore to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with hypoxic-ischaemic encephalopathy. In one of the studies done to assess the intervention that can be undertaken to reduce deaths from birth asphyxia, neonatal resuscitation was found to be a highly effective intervention (Lee et al., 2011).

2.2 Prevalence of Perinatal Asphyxia

Information on the estimates of neonatal mortality is priceless in order to track and evaluate the progress that is being made towards achieving the goal of improving maternal and child health outcomes as contained in SDG three (Maluleke, 2019).

In a study by Andrews, Brouillette, & Brouillette, 2008, estimated that across the globe, 275,000 maternal deaths, 2.7 million neonatal deaths, and 2.6 million third trimester stillbirths occurred in 2015. Ninety-eight percent of these neonatal deaths take place in the developing countries with perinatal asphyxia and birth injuries together contributing to almost 29% of these deaths. This estimation is close to that of Daniel, 2014, who observed in his own study that 3% of approximately 120 million infants born in developing countries develop birth asphyxia with around 900,000 of these newborns dying each year in developing countries. A study conducted in general hospitals in Ethiopia also found out that the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia estimated that the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia was 22.1% (Gebreheat et al.,

2018b). However, Hoque (2017) in his study on the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia with evaluation of risk factors, attributed all the deaths to be due to perinatal asphyxia alone, and not other causes of death among the under-5s.

There have been divergent submissions on the prevalence of PA in Nigeria. West and Opara (2013) conducted a study in a specialist hospital observed that 29.4% of all the babies that were admitted between January and October 2010 had perinatal asphyxia. Afterwards, another study was conducted in a semi-urban setting in the northern part of Nigeria where the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia was revealed to have reduced to 24.7% (Aliyu et al., 2017). However this rate was observed to be slightly higher than the estimated 22.1% prevalence that was obtained in another study conducted in Ethiopia, a counterpart developing country, in the same year (Gebreheat et al., 2018b). These results are nonetheless considerably incongruent when compared with the results obtained in another study conducted in the same year by (Egharevba et al., 2018). In his own study conducted in a rural Nigerian hospital, Egharevba et al. reported that perinatal asphyxia accounted for only 13% of the total number of sick neonates that were admitted in the hospital.

Certain authors have attributed the aforementioned to ambiguity in diagnostic criteria for PA while some others opined that it is sequel to improperly gathered or processed data especially during vital registrations. Similarly, the disparity in the results obtain may be attributed to unavailability of a uniform measurement for the assessment of newborns with perinatal asphyxia in Nigeria. Although the two studies above were conducted in specialist hospitals that served as referral centers for other facilities, the diagnostic indexes for both studies were different. Aliyu et al.

categorized newborns with APGAR score of ≤ 6 within the first minute of life as asphyxiated while Egharevba et al. based the diagnosis on an APGAR score of ≤ 3 in the first five minutes of life. This lack of consistency in the diagnosis of asphyxia was also observed in a study conducted by Solayman et al., (2017) who based their own diagnosis of asphyxia on the history of failure or delayed onset to establish respiration independently after birth, a need for positive pressure ventilation for more than one minute or delayed cry with or without cyanosis in the neonate.

Another factor that may contribute to dissimilarity in the values for the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia is poor incomplete documentation of the parameters for the diagnosis of perinatal asphyxia. This was reported in a study conducted in Ethiopia by Ibrahim, Muhye, and Abdulie (2017) who assessed the prevalence and factors that were associated with birth asphyxia. When the result of the prevalence (2.1%) obtained in this study was compared with the results from a similar study by Gebreheat et al (2018a) which was conducted around the same time in the same country, there is a huge gap that make the results of the two studies almost questionable. It may therefore be inferred that estimation of the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in developing countries are grossly unreliable and may be affected by factors that may be difficult to control in a single study.

2.6 Facility Readiness for the Management of Perinatal Asphyxia

The assessment of the readiness of facilities to manage asphyxia is highly imperative because it will provide sound information on the availability and the quality of asphyxia management services and also helps to target the distribution of resources in the highest area of need as far as the management of PA is concerned

(Burke et al., 2016). The assessment of facility readiness will also provide information on the response of the health system to inputs from national and international organizations and how this response influence health outcomes (World Health Organization (WHO), 2013). While efforts are on to achieve the sustainable development goal 4, it is essential to monitor access to this service. According to WHO (2015), facility readiness is the ability of health facilities to deliver the services offered there which is a prerequisite to service quality. By capacity therefore, this study will assess the presence of trained staff, guidelines, infrastructure, equipment, medicines required for the management of PA.

The rate of mortality during the perinatal period has witnessed little or no improvement in low and middle income countries (LMICs) because policy makers and stake holders do not pay serious attention to newborn care (Graft-johnson et al., 2017a). Graft-johnson et al similarly emphasized that the capacity of health facilities need to be strengthened in order to achieved the desired improvement in the health outcomes and survival of newborns, as they play a vital role in the attainment of significant reduction in perinatal mortality rates. It could therefore be inferred that the preparedness of health facilities in forms of adequate equipment, supplies, structure and human resources is essential for effective management of PA and increased rate of perinatal survival.

Completion of newborn resuscitation training program does not imply that an individual is competent to manage newborns with asphyxia. Each hospital is responsible for determining the level of competence and qualifications required for a healthcare provider to assume clinical responsibility for asphyxia management. The

necessary equipment, medicines, infrastructure, guidelines, and trained staff should be available at the time of delivery to facilitate a rapid transition especially for babies delivered who have no spontaneous breathing or/and have a reduced heart rate of less than 100 beats per minute. Resuscitation with bag and mask is a high-impact intervention that can reduce neonatal deaths in resource-poor countries (Kim et al., 2013). The equipment need to be in working condition and clean (Kamau, 2018).

In a study to assess readiness status for the provision of NR at Naivasha District hospital, it was concluded that once the basic equipment for NR are available, a facility can be considered ready for resuscitation (Tecla et al., 2018). It is consequently fundamental that health facilities are equipped with basic supplies that are required for the management of a newborn with perinatal asphyxia, which according to WHO have been highlighted to be a bag and mask for ventilation, a mucus extractor for suctioning, a source of warmth for thermal protection, and a clock (Oloyede & Udo, 2016) especially in resource poor settings. Similarly, Weiner, (2016) recommended that these supplies and equipment that have been identified to be necessary for a complete resuscitation must be readily available for every birth.

Effective asphyxia management is crucial to reduce mortalities and morbidities attributable to birth asphyxia. Management of asphyxia includes basic resuscitation of the newborn, which can be performed with basic equipment and minimal skills (Kamau, 2018). Continuous periodic training of health care workers is one of the intervention that has directly been linked with improvement of neonatal outcomes (Kamau, 2018). Lack of equipment and training do not pose major barriers to newborn resuscitation in Afghanistan, but providers' knowledge and skills need

strengthening in some areas. Midwives proved to be as capable as doctors of performing newborn resuscitation, which validates the major investment made in midwifery education. Competency-based pre-service and in-service training, complemented by supportive supervision, is an effective way to build providers' capacity to perform newborn resuscitation. This kind of training could also help skilled birth attendants based in the community, at private clinics, or at primary care facilities save the lives of newborns (Kim et al., 2013).

2.6.1 Knowledge of Health Workers on the Management of Asphyxia

Murila et al. (2012) in their study affirmed that asphyxia requires prompt intervention by healthcare providers because it is the most urgent clinical pediatric situation in delivery rooms. It has been documented in literature that nurses and birth attendants provide the major portion of newborn care in the largest part of the world (Wise, 2017). Therefore, adequate knowledge of healthcare providers in the labour room, maternity and neonatal unit on neonatal resuscitation is vital to ensure prompt diagnosis of asphyxia, safety of newborns, as well as initiation of effective management in order to reduce array of sequelae associated with the condition (Murila et al., 2012). One of the effective measures to prevent these deaths is to have skilled birth attendants in neonatal resuscitation. A nationwide training program on neonatal resuscitation in China decreased intrapartum related deaths from 7.5 to 3.4 per 10,000. One of the effective measures to prevent these deaths is to have skilled birth attendants in management of PA (Basu, 2014).

Apprenticeship by neophyte healthcare providers from skilled and experienced colleagues is also a vital element for acquisition of knowledge and development of competence in newborn resuscitation. Murila et al. (2012) reported that medical skills that should have been passed from senior colleagues in the medical profession through regular and adequate interaction remain un-inculcated because the senior colleagues lack the good will, effort and time to model newborn resuscitation and mentor the younger professionals, while the latter group is also impatient to learn, thereby resulting in inadequate knowledge and professional insecurity as far as newborn resuscitation is concerned.

Moreover, several trials have shown that basic neonatal resuscitation training decreases neonatal deaths up to 20% in low-resource settings (Basu, 2014). In a study on the assessment of knowledge on neonatal resuscitation among healthcare providers by Murila et al. (2012), it was observed that more than 70% of care providers possessed inadequate knowledge on the concept. Munezero et al. (2018) reiterate that deficiencies in the knowledge of nurses on management of P A have been asserted in literature. It was observed that though they have some theoretical knowledge, they have very poor practical knowledge in using bag–mask ventilation and chest compression. Thus, workshops are needed on ‘hands on’ demonstration of the first one minute of neonatal resuscitation for the nursing staff (Basu, 2014). One effective measure to prevent these deaths is to have skilled birth attendants in management of PA. Unfortunately, most nursing staff and other health care providers have never received any intensive training in neonatal resuscitation (Basu, 2014).

Literature indicates deficiencies in nurses CPR knowledge and skills. In the western world and other developed countries, nurses CPR knowledge and skills also differs. CPR knowledge and skills depend on how frequent trainings were given. Compulsory training is required every 2 years for employment in all licensed health facilities in the USA.

In service Training for Healthcare Providers in the Management of PA

In a study that was done by Allen et al. (2013) to assess the effectiveness of resuscitation training practices for nurses in Australia, it was concluded that there is no correlation between theoretical knowledge about resuscitation and resuscitation practices. They however suggested that it is the responsibility of educators and clinicians to provide opportunities and support for healthcare providers to maintain their resuscitation knowledge and skills through valid means. One of these as opined by them to include simulation refresher training which has been validated empirically to be positively correlated with extended clinical competence of care providers in newborn resuscitation. Similarly, team-focused simulation sessions appear to improve retention of skills and knowledge and also maintain resuscitation expertise of a large number of staff within a facility.

Apart from improving the competence of providers who are experienced in newborn resuscitation, regular retraining introduces and helps them to learn new resuscitation guidelines that change as new evidences emerge (Allen et al., 2013; \Allen et al., 2017) .

2.8 Barriers to Facility Readiness for Prompt Management of Asphyxia

Although it has been well documented in literature that timely low-cost interventions

help to reduce the occurrence, mortality as well as the morbidity of newborns with PA, empirical studies show that neonatal morbidity in healthcare facilities is still highly prevalent in resource poor settings. Studies have shown that most of the resuscitations carried out in these settings are not done in accordance with the recommended guide and timeline (Clary-muronda, 2018). The common factors that have been identified by healthcare providers to constitute barriers to the management of neonatal resuscitation include (but not limited to) supply and availability of resources; provider related factors like knowledge and perceived competence; and some facility related factors (Clary-muronda, 2018; Morgan et al., 2018).

Nurses working in the labour rooms in USA perceived that skills in neonatal resuscitation were a major barrier as far as their ability to manage newborns with asphyxia is concerned. Whereas Sumankuuro et al. (2018) in their own study in low and middle income settings, concluded that the strategy in place for birth and complication readiness is still in its infancy stage in these settings. For instance, a study conducted in Pakistan further revealed that the barriers affecting the emergency care of neonates can be categorized into three levels, these include individual, system-based and organizational barriers (Id et al., 2019). Infrastructural challenges; shortage of skilled staff; and inadequate medical equipment and essentials were some of the factors that Sumankuuro et al. (2018) affirmed to be related to these three levels.

In a study by Murila et al (2012), more than 70% of healthcare personnel working in labour rooms, maternity (Allen et al., 2013) and neonatal units in Kenya attributed

their inadequate knowledge on management of asphyxia to inadequate training on neonatal resuscitation. This opinion was corroborated by (Kim et al., 2013) who concluded in their study on the assessment of capacity for NR, that lack of competency-based pre-service and in-service training on neonatal resuscitation and lack of supportive supervision by personnel who are skilled in NR are some of the factors that can impinge the competency of providers to perform NR. They similarly observed that lack of supportive supervision and continuing education can also create performance gap, thereby affecting the confidence and competence of healthcare providers in the management of asphyxia. Supervision should move from focus on documentation and paper work to acquisition of expertise in order to serve as role models for providers (Kim et al., 2013).

Furthermore, in India, factors affecting the provision of emergency neonatal care in the labour room as opined by nurse mentors during a qualitative study include shortages in resources, low skill level, poor facility structure and administrative support (Morgan et al., 2018). A similar study affirmed that poor facility layout, problems with local referral system and human resource shortage affected the care provision for neonates with perinatal asphyxia (Vail et al., 2018; Wagner, 2015). These problems may be associated with the nature of the health systems where there is a direction of health related resources away from the poorest citizens in many countries (Wagner, 2015).

In facilities with low caseloads, it will be especially challenging to maintain competence because providers will have limited opportunities to manage asphyxiated newborns. This challenge can be addressed by organizing frequent

refresher in-service training and practice with simulators or anatomical models. These models can be transported to the sites where providers are working in order to minimize shortages that can result when providers will have to travel distances from their facilities to undergo the training.

2.9 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual frameworks that was used for this study was adapted from the theory of planned behavior and the theory of organizational readiness for change.

2.9.1. Theory of Planned Behavior

The theory of planned behaviour was originally initiated in 1967 by Fishbein in an attempt to explain the relationship between attitude and behavior (Tlou, 2009). It is a theory based in social psychology with immense history of success and application in the field (Hale, Householder, & Greene, 2012). As expatiated by Tlou, the theory tries to describe relationship that exists between beliefs, behavior, intentions and attitudes. According to this theory, behavior is believed to be accurately determined by behavioral intention.

According to the theory of planned behaoviuor, human behavior is influenced and guided by three kinds of considerations; these are behavioural beliefs, normative beliefs and control beliefs. Behavioural beliefs produce a favourable or unfavourable attitude toward the behaviour, normative beliefs result in subjective norm and control beliefs give rise to perceived behavioural control. Behavioural intention is formed by the combination of attitude towards the behavior, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. It is believed that perceived behavioural control indirectly influences actual behavior through behavioural intention. The more

favourable an individual's attitude is toward behavior and subjective norm, and the greater the perceived behavioural control, the stronger the person's intention to perform the behaviour in question. Finally, given the sufficient degree of actual control over the behavior, people are expected to carry out their intentions when the opportunity arises.

Perceived behavioural control: this refers to some factors and conditions within a person's environment that determine whether he will be able to carry out the behavior or not. These factors and conditions may present as facilitators or barriers that inhibit the individual's ability to perform the behavior. The presence of facilitating environmental condition will increase the intention of an individual to perform the behavior of intent. These factors also determine how difficult or easy it will be to perform the behaviour of intent as perceived by the individual (Tlou, 2009).

Attitude: this is framed by the individual's beliefs, characteristics and disposition towards an action of intent (Tlou, 2009). Nisson and Earl, (2011) also affirmed that attitude is a belief that engaging in a particular behaviour is positive or negative, and according to them, it is an aggregate of readily accessible beliefs about the outcomes that performance of the behavior will yield. Attitudes can be formed by benefits, background knowledge, values or previous outcomes that have obtained as a result of performing the behavior in the past.

Subjective norm: this is another factor that can influence an individual's intention for performing a behaviour (Tlou, 2009). It is perceived to result from social pressure to carry out or not carry out a certain behavior. This is determined by whether significant individuals to a person give approval for a certain behavior or not and the

expected level of compliance with the behavior (Tlou, 2009). The weight of reference ascribed to these significant individuals determines attitude towards perform the action (Tlou, 2009).

Figure 2.4: Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991, p.182, as cited in Tlou, 2009, p. 54)

2.9.2. The Theory of Organizational Readiness for Change

Readiness for change refers to organizational members' shared resolve to implement a change (change commitment) and their shared belief in their collective capability to bring about the change (change efficacy) (Weiner, 2009). Similarly, Weiner explained that readiness is a state of being both physically and psychologically ready to take an action. Change commitment and change efficacy are similar to the perceived behavioural control component of the theory of planned behavior. The theory of organizational readiness presents how organizational structures, resources and endowments shape readiness perceptions by members of an organization.

The perceived readiness of an organization is dependent on the values that members of the organization place upon the resultant effect of the change and how favourably they evaluate the availability of the key determinants of the organization's capacity to implement the change (Weiner, 2009). Weiner opined that the major factors that determine an organization's capability to implement a change include task demands (by consumers), availability of resources and situational factors. The more available the key determinants for implementing a change, the higher the level of readiness for change in an organization (Weiner, 2009).

Organizational readiness indicates the relationship between people, processes, systems and performance measurement. This was corroborated by Weiner (2009) who reiterated that ability of an organization to implement a change is greatly determined by shared resolution of the members of the organization to effect the change. It requires synchronization and coordination of the many people that contribute to the implementation, without which no implementation will be successful.

The rationale for readiness of an organization includes improvement in productivity and efficiency, reduction in cost, increased quality and responsiveness, reduction in variation in practice and increased access to health services (Sales, 2009). The assessment of organization readiness is vital to determining how ready an organization is to make changes to conform to new evidence based practices (Sales, 2009). In other words, organizational members take into consideration the organization's structural assets and deficits in formulating their change efficacy judgments.

Perceived Behavioural Control: this has been described as both internal and external factors which makes the performance of a behavior easy or difficult for an individual (Nisson & Earl, 2011). These factors as emphasized by (B. J. Weiner, 2009) may include material, financial, human and informational resources that are available in an organization to enact the target behavior, which may or may not be within the individual's control. For this study, some of the factors may include the physical structure and equipment accessible in the facility for the management of perinatal asphyxia, pre and in-service training of healthcare providers, availability of basic medication and other supplies, communication and transportation facilities.

Attitude: The basic training, perceived abilities (competence) and level of confidence of healthcare providers will determine their disposition towards carrying out carrying out resuscitation for a newborn with asphyxia. Professional training/education of labor room personnel, outcomes of previous managed cases, previous experience in the care of asphyxiated babies, facility level are all vital to build the confidence of healthcare providers in their abilities to manage perinatal asphyxia, boost their efficacy in the procedure, and therefore culminate in a positive attitude to engage in the procedure whenever the need arises for it.

Subjective norm: provision of human, material and financial resources, national health policy on management of PA, facility policy and protocols on management of PA, regular monitoring and evaluation of personnel efficiency, mentoring and supervision by colleagues who have better proficiency in the procedure and documentation protocol are the responsibilities of the facility administrators at different levels. The adequacy of these will determine the outcomes expected based

on the input.

Figure 2.5: The Theory of Organizational Readiness for Change (Weiner, 2009)

2.9.3. Framework for this study

Measuring readiness is a systematic analysis of an organization's ability to undertake a transformational process or change. These transformational processes often include both physical preparations and trainings for emergencies, thus necessitating research, estimation, planning, resourcing, education, practicing and rehearsing. In the context of this study, the readiness assessment identified the potential challenges that might arise when implementing procedures, structures, and processes within a current organizational context. Some of these challenges are related to institutional factors in form of policies, leadership, infrastructure, procurement of supplies and equipment, human resources, or provider related factors like attitude, perceived behavioural control and subjective norm. All these

factors can influence the effectiveness of the management of newborn asphyxia in a health facility, which in turn have a cumulative effect on the health outcome of asphyxiated newborn babies that are cared for in such facilities. Therefore, the extent to which these changes are adopted at both institutional and individual (healthcare providers') level is the extent to which the health facility is ready to manage perinatal asphyxia, which will be an effective intervention to drastically reduce the rate of mortality resulting from perinatal asphyxia in Osun State.

Figure 2.6: Conceptual Model for the Study. Adapted from Weiner and Tlou)

2.13 Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant association between providers' job category and their knowledge in the management of perinatal asphyxia.
2. There is no significant association between the level of a health facility and knowledge of healthcare providers in the management of perinatal asphyxia.
3. There is no significant relationship between healthcare providers' years of experience and their knowledge in the management of perinatal asphyxia.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the various methods that were employed in carrying out this study. These include the research design, research setting, the target population, the sample and sampling technique, instrument for data collection, validity and reliability of the instrument, the procedure for the data collection and then, the method of data analysis.

3.1 Research Design :

The study adopted an embedded (mixed) method research design. This method is a design in which a data set provides a supportive and secondary role in a study that is based on the primary data set. The primary data set for this study was elicited using a standard questionnaire, facility inventory checklist and review of delivery registers. The secondary data set was generated with an in-depth interview guide. The qualitative data was collected after the quantitative data in order to further substantiate and provide an in-depth follow-up on the qualitative data. This method was adopted because of its focus on collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study (Creswell & Clark, 2014). The basic

goal of using mixed method research design in this study is not to replace either quantitative or qualitative approach but rather to draw from strengths of the two methods and minimize the weaknesses of both in this research study (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). A tested and validated structured instrument (questionnaire) was used to assess the knowledge of health workers and facility readiness for the management of PA in selected health facilities in Osun State; prevalence of perinatal asphyxia was estimated by reviewing the delivery records of the facilities from January to December, 2019.

3.2 Research Setting

This facility-based study was conducted across the three levels of health facilities across Osun State. Osun State was created on August 27th, 1991. It is located within latitude 6.550 and 8.100 north and longitude 3.550 and 5.050 east. It covers total landmass of about 12,820 square kilometers. Recently, it was estimated that Osun State has an population of about 4,705,600 inhabitants, made up of 1,740,619 males and 1,682,916 females (Osun State Governmnet, 2017). The State has over 200 towns, several villages and settlements. The indigenes are predominantly farmers, traders and artisans who belong to the Yoruba tribe.

For administrative purpose, the state is divided into three Senatorial Districts, 6 administrative zones, 67 local government areas, Local Council/Development Areas, and Area offices. The Senatorial districts include Osun I (West), Osun II (Central), and Osun III (East) and each of the senatorial districts has two administrative zones. Osun I comprises of Ede and Iwo zones; Osun II is made up of Osogbo and Ikirun zones; while Osun III consist of Ilesha and Ife zones. Similarly, each of the senatorial

districts has ten local governments (Osun State Government, 2018). The study was conducted in the three senatorial districts, namely Osun central, Osun west and Osun east senatorial districts.

The total number of government owned health facilities in the state is eight hundred and one (801), which include seven hundred and forty six (746) primary health facilities, fifty two (52) secondary health facilities and three (3) tertiary health facilities (Osun State Ministry of Health, 2016). The three levels of health facilities- primary, secondary and tertiary were included in the setting of the study. However, this study was conducted in twenty health facilities that were selected randomly across six local government areas which spanned the three senatorial districts.

3.3 Target Population:

This included doctors, nurses and community health workers that attend to deliveries in the selected health facilities.

3.4 Sample Size Determination:

The sample size for this study included healthcare providers working in the three levels of the selected health facilities who meet the inclusion criteria during the study period.

3.4.1 Quantitative

The sample size for the quantitative study was calculated using Yamane's simplified sample formula for proportions:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (e)^2}$$

Source: (Glenn, 1997)

Where n= sample size,

N= the population size (220) and,

e= level of precision (0.05).

With the above formula,

n = 141.9

In order to adjust the sample size because of 10% non-response rate, the sample size was adjusted to 156 participants.

For the qualitative aspect, 20 healthcare providers who participated in the quantitative aspect of the study were interviewed based on the concept of saturation.

3.4.2 Inclusion criteria

- Healthcare providers who have a minimum of 6 months working experience in the labour room.
- Healthcare providers attending to deliveries in each health facility will be included
- Healthcare providers who give consent to participate in the study

3.4.3 Exclusion criteria

- Healthcare providers who decline participation
- Healthcare providers that do not attend to deliveries will not be included in the study

3.5 Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was used in selecting samples for this study, and the three stages used are as follows;

3.5.1 Selection of Senatorial Districts, Administrative Zones and Local Government Areas

This is stage where the selection of Senatorial districts, administrative zones and Local Government Areas (LGAs) for this study was done.

All the three Senatorial districts the six administrative zones in Osun State were purposively selected for the study. There are 10 LGAs in each senatorial district, while each administrative zone is made up of 5 LGs. Furthermore, 20% of the LGAs in each district were selected randomly for this study. Thus, one local government was randomly selected from each administrative zone. Therefore, a total of six local governments were selected for the study. The local governments that were selected are Ife Central, Ilesa West, Ede North, Iwo, Ifelodun and Osogbo local governments. (Figure 3.1)

3.5.2 Selection of Health Facilities

From each of the six LGAs selected two primary health facilities and one secondary health facility were randomly selected; while two out the three tertiary health facilities in the State were included in the study. (Figure 3.1)

3.5.3 Selection of Healthcare Providers

The healthcare providers that met the inclusion criteria were randomly selected based on the concept of proportional allocation such that the samples from each facility level are kept proportional to the sample frame in each facility level using the formula for proportional allocation; (Figure 3.2)

$$N_1 = n \cdot \frac{N_1}{N}$$

Source: (Kothari, 2004)

Where N_1 is the sample size for primary facilities, N_2 is the sample size for secondary facilities and N_3 is the sample size for tertiary facilities,

NJ is the sampling frame for each facility level,

N is the population size, and

n is the sample size for the study.

Using the formula above, the sample size for each population is as follows:

Primary health facilities = 44 participants

Secondary health facilities = 47 participants

Tertiary health facilities = 65 participants

Table 3.1 List of the Administrative Zones, LGAs, Primary, Secondary and Tertiary Facilities

Senatorial Districts	Administrative Zones	LGAs	Primary Facilities	Secondary Facilities	Tertiary Facilities
Osun East	Ife	Ife Central	Primary Health center (PHC) Enuwa, Ile-Ife	State Hospital, Oke Ogbo, Ile-Ife	Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife
			Comprehensive Health Center, Arubiewe		
	Ilesa	Ilesa West	Isokun PHC, Ilesa	State Hospital, Ilesa	
			Irebami PHC, Ilesa		
Osun West	Ede	Ede North	Oja Timi PHC, Ede	State Hospital,	

				Cottage, Ede	
			Oke Gada PHC, Ede		
	Iwo	Iwo	Alaye PHC, Iwo	State hospital, Iwo	
			Ikoyi PHC, Iwo		
Osun central	Osogbo	Osogbo	Atelewo PHC, Osogbo	State Hospital, Asubiaro, OSogbo	LAUTECH Teaching Hospital, Osogbo
			Oke Baale PHC, Osogbo		
	Ikirun	Ifelodun	Okeamola PHC, Ikirun	State Hospital, Ikirun	
			Akinorun PHC, Ikirun		

Table 3.2 Distribution of Healthcare Providers in the Selected Health Facilities

S/N	Health Facilities	Number of Healthcare Providers	Number of Selected Healthcare Providers
	Primary Health Facilities		
1.	PHC Enuwa, Ile-Ife	7	5
2.	CHC, Arubiewe, Ile-Ife	2	1
3.	Isokun PHC, Ilesa	5	4
4.	Irebami PHC, Ilesa	3	2
5.	Oja Timi PHC, Ede	7	5
6.	Oke Gada PHC, Ede	5	4
7.	Alaye PHC, Iwo	4	3
8.	Ikoyi PHC, Iwo	5	4

9.	Atelewo PHC, Osogbo	6	4
10.	Oke Baale PHC, Osogbo	6	4
11.	Okeamola PHC, Ikirun	6	4
12.	Akinorun PHC, Ikirun	6	4
	Total	63	44
	Percentage of sample size		28.2%
	Secondary Health Facilities		
13.	State Hospital, Oke Ogbo, Ile-Ife	10	7
14.	State Hospital, Ilesa	8	6
15.	State Hospital, Cottage, Ede	12	9
16.	State hospital, Iwo	10	7
17.	State Hospital, Asubiaro, Osogbo	16	11
18.	State Hospital, Ikirun	10	7
	Total	66	47
	Percentage of sample size		30.1%
	Tertiary Health Facilities		
19.	Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife	49	35
20.	LAUTECH Teaching Hospital, Osogbo	43	30
	Total	92	65
	Percentage of sample size		41%

3.6 Instruments of Data Collection

Four instruments were used for data collection in this study, namely; facility caseload review checklist, healthcare providers' knowledge assessment questionnaire, checklist for the assessment of facility readiness for the management of PA and an in-depth interview guide.

3.6.1 Perinatal Asphyxia Prevalence Checklist

Using this instrument, the delivery registers, case notes and report books from January to December, 2019 were reviewed to elicit data on the total number of life

births, still births and asphyxiated babies over the period so specified. Approximately, records of 6288 newborns were reviewed in the selected facilities between January and December, 2019. A baby was considered to be asphyxiated if the APGAR score was ≤ 6 or was reported not to have cried well at 1 and 5 minutes of birth. However, caution should be taken in interpreting the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in primary healthcare facilities because the record of APGAR scores in these facilities was grossly deficient due to actual unavailability of record and inaccuracy in the measurement of the APGAR scores that were recorded.

3.6.2 Structured Questionnaire

This instrument was adapted from the Service Provision Assessment (SPA) survey, Service Availability and Readiness Assessment (SARA) tool and textbook of neonatal resuscitation, 6th edition. SPA is a survey tool that was developed by the United State Agency for International Development (USAID) for assessing the types of services available in health facilities and the extent to which health facilities are ready to provide such services. The SARA tool was developed by the WHO in collaboration with USAID (WHO, 2015) to monitor service delivery at various facility levels. These tools have been tested in previous studies for both validity and reliability and they include numerous indicators on newborn care. The facility inventory questionnaire included in the SPA survey was used to obtain data in the following domains: health facility infrastructure, supplies, medicines, staffing, training and procedures. Similarly, the questionnaire was used to collect information on the experience, qualifications and perceived barriers to the management of PA.

Section A: consists of 19 questions that will be used to elicit information on the

socio-demographic characteristics and other background information from the participants.

Section B: consists of 38 items that were used to assess the knowledge of participants on the equipment (basic resuscitation equipment- 8 items; advanced resuscitation equipment- 10 items), medications (11 items) and supplies (9 items) that were required, available and functioning in their facilities for basic and advanced management of PA.

Section C: Contains 73 items adapted from the textbook of neonatal resuscitation (6th edition) which will be used to assess the knowledge of participants on the management of PA. The specific domains that were assessed include: preparation for the management of perinatal asphyxia (9 items), some predisposing factors to perinatal asphyxia (5 items), diagnostic signs (5 items), preliminary steps of management (12 items), what to do when resuscitating with bag and mask (12 items), managing a baby that is breathing with no respiratory difficulty (4 items), managing a baby that does not begin breathing, heart rate is less than 60bpm, or if there is intercostals retraction or grunting within 20 minutes of management (10 items), and post resuscitation management (12 items), post-procedure tasks (4 items).

Section D: This consists of 22 questions that were adapted from review of literature; SARA and SPA survey tools to assess the availability of job aids, supervision and facility support for the management of PA in the facilities. The domains that were assessed include the following: job aids (3 items), supervision (5 items) and facility support for asphyxia management (14 items).

3.6.3 Facility Readiness Checklist

This was used by the researcher and trained research assistants to take the inventory of the available human resources, infrastructure, communication, transport, services that are provided, equipment for basic and advanced newborn resuscitation, medication, supplies, and clinical guidelines for the management of PA in each of the facilities.

Section A: consists of items that were used to assess availability of personnel, infrastructure, communication, ambulance for transport and referral system during emergencies, power supply, water supply, processing of equipment for reuse and availability of resuscitation guideline in the labour room.

Section B: consists of 10 items that were used to assess service availability

Section C: This consists of items that assessed the availability and status (functioning and ready for use) of equipment, supplies and medications that are required for the management of PA. The following were the indicators of availability and readiness for equipment and supplies that were required for PA management: basic equipment (8 items), advanced equipment (10 items), other supplies (10 items) and medications (12 items)

3.6.4 In-depth Interview Guide

The in-depth interview guide was developed by the researcher based on review of literature to obtain data on perceived barriers to the management of PA. The interview guide consists of 11 probing questions for the respondents. All the interview sessions were audio-recorded with the permission of the interviewees and thereafter transcribed verbatim.

3.7 Ethical Consideration

Ethical approvals to conduct the study were obtained from Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, LAUTECH Teaching Hospital and Osun State Hospitals' Management Board (OSHMB) with the following approval numbers; ERC/2020/02/02, LTH/EC/2020/02/450 from the two teaching hospitals while the approval from OSHMB does not have an approval number. Letters of permission to conduct the study were obtained from the appropriate authorities in the selected health facilities. A letter introducing the researcher and the study was given to each participant and written consents were obtained before participation in the study. Participants were offered detailed information concerning the purpose of the study, benefits of participation, procedure of the study and the proposed duration of the study. Furthermore, before the commencement of the study, participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any point during the study for reasons best known without any consequence. Their fundamental human rights to confidentiality of information, anonymity of persons, were duly revered throughout the period of data collection.

3.8 Pilot Study

The pilot study was conducted in Oyo North Senatorial District in Oyo State. Two Local Government Areas (Ogbomosho North and Ogbomosho South) were selected from the Senatorial District to conduct the pilot study. Three health facilities (Bowen University Teaching Hospital and Okelerin Primary health center in Ogbomosho North LGA; and State Hospital Ogbomosho in Ogbomosho South LGA) were

purposively selected for the pilot study. The pilot study was conducted among nurses and doctors working in the labour rooms and newborn intensive care units of the selected health facilities. The pilot study assessed the prevalence, knowledge of healthcare providers on the management, facility readiness and barriers to the management of perinatal asphyxia between the periods of September 1st and October 14th 2019.

The purpose of the pilot study was to determine the feasibility of this research study. The pilot study also tested whether the questionnaire was comprehensible and appropriate, and that the questions were not ambiguous, and that they are presented in a consistent manner. The four instruments that were used for the pilot study include; questionnaire, prevalence estimation checklist, facility readiness checklist and an in-depth interview guide. The questionnaire for the respondents was divided into four sections which include; socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge of asphyxia management, facility readiness for delivery of the management of PA, and barriers to facility readiness for asphyxia management.

During the pilot study, the provisional study protocol was strictly adhered to from the recruitment of the subjects, data collection to data analysis. The time taken to explain the research project and obtain consent from the participants was about 8-10 minutes. It took about 40-45 minutes to complete a questionnaire, and about 25-45 minutes to conclude an interview session. Thus, the need to recruit more than two research assistants for data collection during the main study in order to cover the stipulated participant and to save time in order to meet up with time line for this study. The research instruments have therefore been modified based on the results

obtained from the pilot study.

3.9 Validity of the Instruments

The instruments were developed and designed in congruence with the topic, the items included in the instruments are based on the study objectives and the items included in the instruments were adapted from standardized and tested survey tools as established by reviewed literatures. The instruments were reviewed and ascertained for content and face validity before established before implementing the study. The content validity was ascertained by checking the measurement against the conceptual definitions of the constructs that the instruments are intended to measure. Similarly, after analyzing data from the pilot study, it was observed that scores of participants on some measures correlate with other variables that they were expected to correlate with based on the results from previous studies. The instruments were afterwards given to the project supervisor and other experts in relevant fields for face validity check.

3.10 Reliability of the Instruments

A validity test was conducted using Spearman Pearson correlation, and the correlation value (r) was found to be 0.876* which indicates a good internal consistency of the instrument.

The Cronbach alpha coefficient for the instruments was evaluated to be 0.952.

3.11 Procedure for Data Collection

The process for data collection for this study was in four phases as discussed in the following paragraphs:

3.11.1 Estimation of the Prevalence of Perinatal Asphyxia

Facility caseload review was done by reviewing the delivery registers and report books of each facility for the months of January till December, 2019. The total number of records that were reviewed is 6288, included were the records of all the newborns that were delivered in the labour units and all newborns that were admitted in the newborn care units of the selected health facilities. Similarly, the records of newborns that were assessed to have an AGGAR score of less than 7 within the 1st and 5th minute of life in the labour units and those admitted in the newborn care units with a diagnosis of birth/perinatal asphyxia were then reviewed. Thereafter, the percentage of those who had asphyxia was obtained for each facility, after which the overall average was estimated.

3.11.2 Assessment of Healthcare Providers Knowledge on Management of PA

This phase involved obtaining permission from the gatekeepers of selected health facilities and informed consent from the study participants. The investigator thereafter went to each unit with the letter of introduction from the department and a copy of ethical clearance that was previously obtained from gatekeepers. A brief description, purpose and objectives of the study was provided for each respondent on the first page of the questionnaire after which questions on how to fill the questionnaires were answered. Questionnaires were thereafter distributed to respondents who gave their consent to participate and met the inclusion criteria; none of the participants was coerced to participate. Due to the busy schedules of the respondents, it was not possible to retrieve most of the questionnaires on the

day of distribution. However, the participants gave a date when the questionnaires would have been completed. The questionnaires were observed for completeness. The rights of the respondents to privacy and confidentiality were duly protected by making sure that no means of identification is provided on the questionnaires by respondents.

3.11.3 Assessment of Facility Readiness for the Management of PA

The facility readiness checklists were given to the Head Nurse in each unit for reported service availability and readiness, the researcher afterwards took a record of observed availability and readiness for the management of PA. The availability and readiness was thereafter estimated by calculating the mean availability of service-specific tracer items in the following domains: personnel available and relevant training in the management of PA in the last 12 months, availability of basic equipment required for the management of PA, availability of medications, other supplies and flow chart for management of PA. The assessment was done using the following criteria:

Personnel availability and readiness: The target score for the availability of core medical professionals is 23 for tertiary and secondary levels of health facilities and 11.5 for primary health facilities (WHO, 2015). The core medical professionals include physicians, non-physicians, registered nurses and midwives (WHO, 2015). Only healthcare providers that fall in this job category were included in the estimation of personnel available for the management of PA. A score of 1 is given when a medical professional is available on full time basis while those available on part-time basis will be scored 0.5 (WHO, 2015). Similarly, the knowledge score and

recent (in the past 24 months) in-service training was included in the criteria for the assessment of personnel readiness in each facility.

Equipment for basic resuscitation: The basic equipment that were assessed include ambu bag and mask (sizes 0 and 1), thermometer, resuscitation table and pre-warmed towels (or resuscitaire), stethoscope, suction apparatus (electric suction machine, bulb syringe or mucus extractor), light source and a clock with seconds hand. The assessment included equipment that were available at the labour unit in a clean condition and functioning.

Medications and other supplies: this included the availability of essential drugs like 0.9% normal saline, 10% dextrose water, adrenaline, and phenobarbitone. The essential supplies that were assessed for the management of PA included methylated spirit, syringes (1mL, 2mL, 5mL, and 10mL), antiseptic lotion, water-proof tape or securing device and Sterile gloves.

Amenities (Infrastructure): this included the availability electric power and alternative source of supply, mobile phone for communication, portable water supply, availability of an ambulance in a working condition for emergency transfer, a flowchart or guideline for the management of PA in the labour room and referral forms as at the time the assessment was made.

3.11.4 Exploration of the Barriers to the management of PA

Interview sessions on the barriers to the management of PA were conducted with respondents that participated in the quantitative aspect of the study. A total of 20 healthcare providers were randomly selected from the selected health facilities, using the principle of saturation. The participants who participated gave written

consents for the session to be conducted and recorded before the commencement of the interview sessions. Each interview session took place for about 25-42 minutes and was recorded using an audio recorder. The data collection for this qualitative aspect was discontinued when it was observed that no new information or theme was emerging from the last three participants that were interviewed. It was thereafter concluded that saturation had been reached.

3.11 Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaires that were returned from respondents that participated willfully after fulfilling the inclusion criteria were assessed for completeness. The completed questionnaires were then sorted for coding before entering the data on Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 23. Later, descriptive (mean, frequency and percentages) analysis was used for analyzing the data. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed with simple descriptive statistics, using frequency tables and percentages. Meanwhile, the relationship and differences between dependent and independent variables were tested using bivariate analysis.

Objective 1: To estimate the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in health facilities Osun state.

This objective was answered by analyzing data from reviewed birth registers, case notes and report books of the facilities. The estimated number of life births was divided by the number of asphyxiated newborns in year 2019.

Objective 2: To assess the knowledge of health workers on neonatal resuscitation in

health facilities in Osun State on. Health workers' knowledge was assessed on requirements and steps of basic newborn resuscitation. This was done using a structured personnel interview tool that is a component of SARA. A knowledge score of 80 and above will be categorized as good and a score of 79 and less will be categorized as poor.

Objective 3: To assess extent of facility readiness for delivery of neonatal resuscitation in health facilities in Osun State. This objective was answered by the facility inventory questionnaire, which is the second instrument in this study. The instrument was used specifically to assess the facilities for availability of the basic requirements which include personnel available, facility infrastructure; essential equipment, supplies and medicines for the management of PA.

Personnel available: the domains that were assessed for personnel availability and readiness were number of skilled healthcare providers (medical doctors and nurses), training in the management of newborns with PA (neonatal resuscitation) in the past 2 years

Facility infrastructure: this will include availability of a mobile phone for communication, delivery register, newborn care corner, ambulance for emergency transportation, regular power supply (including a generator that is fueled as at the time of taking this inventory) and water supply in the facility at the time of taking this inventory. A score of 1 was allocated to availability of a mobile phone with call cards that are made available by the facility management; a score of 1 is allocated for availability of a delivery register that is completed, 0.5 to a delivery register that is partly completed and zero to a delivery register that is not completed at all; a score

of 1 is allocated to the availability of an ambulance that is functioning and fueled by the facility management on the day of taking this inventory, 0.5 is allotted if not functioning nor fueled and zero if not available at all; a score of 1 was given if there was availability of electric power supply and a back up (generator that is fueled by the facility), 0.5 if there was electric power supply but no back up, and 0 if there was neither electric power supply nor a backup; while a score of 1 was allocated if there was a supply of portable water within the facility and 0 zero if there was no means of water supply within the facility premises.

Equipment: the equipment required for the basic management of PA were assessed for availability and functionality (in a ready for use condition). A score of 1 was allotted if the equipment was available, functioning and in a ready for use condition; 0.5 if available but not functioning or ready for use; and 0 if not available at all. Any facility that has all the basic equipment for newborn resuscitation in a ready for use condition will be considered ready to manage PA in this domain of assessment (Weiner, 2016; WHO, 2015).

Medicines and supplies: Basically, the medications required for the basic management of a newborn with asphyxia were assessed for availability. Other supplies that were required for the administration of the medications were also considered. A medicine in the facilities was considered available and scored 1, if it is supplied by the government and if it has not expired, 0.5 if it is available within the facility but will be paid for by the patients and 0 if not available at all. A facility will be regarded as ready if it has the basic medications required for the management of asphyxia (Weiner, 2016; WHO, 2015).

Objective 4: To identify the barriers to prompt management of birth asphyxia in health facilities in Osun State. This was assessed using an interview guide for personnel at managerial levels in the selected facilities. The responses of these personnel to the interview questions regarding barriers to prompt management of asphyxia will be coded and a matrix of responses will be done, so as to outline major themes that emerged from the responses.

The responses were be recorded using a voice recorder. The audio record of the responses of these administrators in English language was transcribed verbatim. These transcripts were then subjected to reading and re-reading in order to get a broad picture of the responses. Themes were thereafter identified before a contextual coding of the themes.

Table 3.3: List of Objectives and Method of Analysis

S/N	Objectives	Research Design	Source of Data	Research Instruments	Data Analysis
1.	To estimate the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in health facilities in Osun State	Quantitative	Facility registers, case notes and report books	Facility caseload checklist	Descriptive
2.	To assess the knowledge of management of PA among healthcare providers in health facilities in Osun State	Quantitative	Healthcare providers in selected health facilities	Structured knowledge assessment questionnaire	Descriptive
3.	To assess the extent of facility readiness for the management of PA in health facilities in Osun State.	Quantitative	Direct observation of the structure, availability of equipment and supplies and conditions of the equipment in the facilities	Facility inventory checklist	Descriptive
4.	To explore the barriers to management of PA in health facilities in Osun State.	Qualitative	Healthcare providers who have performed at least 3 newborn resuscitation before	Semi-structured interview guide	Content and thematic analysis

Table 3.4: List of hypotheses and method of analysis

S/N	Statement of Hypothesis	Method of Analysis
1.	There is no significant association between providers' job category and their knowledge in the management of perinatal asphyxia.	ANOVA
2.	There is no significant association between the level of a health facility and knowledge of healthcare providers in the management of perinatal asphyxia	ANOVA
3.	There is no significant relationship between healthcare providers' years of experience and their knowledge in the management of perinatal asphyxia	T-test

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

The focus of this research was to assess the knowledge of healthcare providers and the readiness of health facilities for the management of PA. This chapter presents the findings of the studies among the selected population. A total of 156 healthcare providers were enrolled in the study while records of 6288 newborns that were delivered and admitted in the selected health facilities between January and December 2019 were reviewed. The results of the study are presented in this chapter under the following sub-topics:

- 4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics the study participants
- 4.2 Prevalence of perinatal asphyxia
- 4.3 Knowledge of healthcare providers on the management of PA
- 4-4 Facility readiness for the management of PA
- 4.5 Barriers to the management of PA
- 4.6 Testing of Hypotheses

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4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics the study participants

Table 4.1.1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents for Quantitative Study

Characteristics	Facility level			Total (N=156)
	Primary (n=49)	Secondary (n=44)	Tertiary (n=63)	
Age group (mean=38.5; SD=9.2)				
20 – 29	4 (8.2)	4 (9.1)	19 (30.2)	27 (17.3)
30 – 39	18 (36.7)	11 (25.0)	28 (44.4)	57 (36.5)
40 – 49	21 (42.9)	16 (36.4)	15 (23.8)	52 (33.3)
50 – 59	6 (12.2)	13 (29.5)	1 (16)	20 (12.8)
Sex				
Male	2 (4.1)	9 (20.5)	7 (11.1)	18 (11.5)
Female	47 (95.9)	35 (79.5)	56 (88.9)	138 (88.5)
Marital status				
Single	6 (12.2)	2 (4.5)	13 (20.6)	21 (13.5)
Married	40 (81.6)	42 (95.5)	48 (76.2)	130 (83.3)
Others	3 (6.1)	0 (0.0)	2 (3.2)	5 (3.2)
Religion				
Christianity	41 (83.7)	29 (65.9)	54 (85.7)	124 (79.5)
Islam	8 (16.3)	15 (34.1)	9 (14.3)	32 (20.5)
Job category				

Characteristics	Facility level			Total
General Nurses	3 (6.1)	5 (11.4)	4 (6.4)	12 (7.7)
Nurse with Specialization	10 (20.4)	24 (54.5)	45 (71.4)	79 (50.6)
Medical Officer	3 (6.1)	13 (29.5)	3 (4.8)	19 (12.2)
Medical Officer with Specialization	0 (0.0)	2 (4.6)	11 (17.5)	13 (8.3)
Community Health Practitioners	33 (67.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	33 (21.2)
Ward unit				
Labor ward	0 (0.0)	17 (38.6)	29 (46.0)	46 (29.5)
Maternity	49 (100.0)	20 (45.4)	0 (0.0)	69 (44.2)
Newborn	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	34 (54.0)	34 (21.8)
Theater	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	7 (4.5)
Management of PA as a responsibility				
No	9 (18.4)	2 (4.6)	1 (1.6)	12 (7.7)
Yes	40 (81.6)	42 (95.4)	62 (98.4)	144 (92.3)
Years of experience				
1 – 5	2 (4.1)	10 (22.7)	19 (30.2)	31 (19.9)
6 – 10	8 (16.3)	10 (22.7)	23 (36.5)	41 (26.3)
11 – 15	17 (34.7)	10 (22.7)	10 (15.9)	37 (23.7)
16 – 20	15 (30.6)	2 (4.6)	6 (9.5)	23 (14.7)
21 – 25	1 (2.0)	11 (25.0)	3 (4.8)	15 (9.6)
26 – 30	6 (12.2)	1 (2.3)	2 (3.2)	9 (5.8)

As illustrated in table 4.1 above, more than a quarter (40.4%) of the healthcare providers recruited for the quantitative aspect of the study work in tertiary healthcare facilities while about a quarter (31.4%) work in primary healthcare facilities and the remaining 28.2% work in secondary healthcare facilities. Most (83.3%) of the respondents were married with less than half (36.5%) at 30-39 years of age and majority (88.5%) of female gender. In addition, a greater part (79.5%) of the respondents were Christians while almost half (44.2%) of were registered midwives. All respondents sampled in primary facility and majority (45.5%) in secondary facility work in maternity unit and more than half (53.9%) in tertiary facility work in newborn

units. Approximately 98% of respondents in tertiary facility, 95% in secondary facility and 82% in primary facility considered the management of perinatal asphyxia part of responsibility in their respective facility.

Table 4.1.2: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants for Qualitative study

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	2	10.0
Female	18	90.0
Age (mean = 39.9;SD=7.2) in years		
Less than 30	1	5.0
30 – 39	10	50.0
40 – 49	7	35.0
50+	2	10.0
Facility level		
Primary	12	60.0
Secondary	6	30.0
Tertiary	2	10.0
Job category		

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Pediatrician	1	5.0
Community Health Practitioner	6	30.0
General Medical Doctor	1	5.0
Graduate Nurse	4	20.0
Midwife	6	30.0
Pediatric Nurse	2	10.0
Designation		
Assistant Chief Nursing Officer	8	40.0
Assistant Director Nursing Officer	1	5.0
Community Health Officer (Senior/Junior)	6	30.0
House officer	1	5.0
Principal nursing officer	3	15.0
Senior Registrar	1	5.0
Years of experience (mean=15.1;SD=5.4)		
Less than 10	3	15.0
11 – 15	6	30.0
16+	11	55.0

Majority (90%) of the participants for the qualitative study were females (Table 4.1.2). A greater percentage of them work in primary health facilities while majority are aged between 30-39 years. Community health practitioners (CHP) and midwives each form 30% of the population, with only one (5%) each of pediatrician and general medical doctor. The number of participants with less than 10 years of experience was minimal (15%) while a greater number (55%) have been working for more than 16 years.

4.2: The Prevalence of Perinatal Asphyxia in the Selected Health Facilities

Figure 4.1: Prevalence of Perinatal Asphyxia in Year 2019

Figure 4.2: Prevalence of PA in the Three Facility Levels

Overall, PA is most prevalent in the tertiary level of health facilities (Fig. 4.1 and Figure 4.2), peaking at 18.% and 18.% in the months of April and December respectively (Fig. 4.1). The lowest rates were observed in May and July when both the tertiary and primary level facilities experienced a dip to 8.% (July) and 8.% (May) respectively (Fig. 4.1). The rate maxed out to 16.% (Fig. 4.2) in September across the selected primary health facilities, and in the whole, the rate was observed to be slightly higher throughout the year when compared with the prevalence rate obtained in the secondary facilities, that is 11.6% and 11.7% in secondary and primary facilities respectively (Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.3: Prevalence of PA Across all Levels

Results of this study showed that in year 2019, 12.7% of all the babies that were born and admitted within the perinatal period in the selected facilities had PA (Figure 4.3).

4.3 Knowledge of Healthcare Providers on the Management of PA

Table 4.3.1: Knowledge of Healthcare Providers on Specific Steps in the Management of PA

Indicators	Number of items	Maximum obtainable scores	Mean knowledge score for asphyxia management by Facility level			
			All (N=156)	Primary (N=49)	Secondary (N=44)	Tertiary (N=63)
			Mean (%)	Mean (%)	Mean (%)	Mean (%)
Basic resuscitation equipment	8	16	13.2 (82.5)	11.6 (72.5)	13.2 (82.5)	14.3 (89.4)
Medications and supplies that are required	11	22	19.5 (88.6)	16.3 (74.1)	20.6 (93.6)	21.2 (96.4)
Preparation for the management of asphyxia	9	18	16.7 (92.8)	15.5 (86.1)	17.2 (95.6)	17.3 (96.1)
Factors that predispose a baby to asphyxia	5	10	7.4 (74.0)	6.8 (68.0)	7.7 (77.0)	7.7 (77.0)
Signs to be present before diagnosis	5	10	9.1 (91.0)	8.3 (83.0)	9.1 (91.0)	9.6 (96.0)
Preliminary steps in asphyxia management	12	24	17.9 (74.6)	17.2 (71.7)	18.4 (76.7)	18.0 (75.0)
What to be done:						
When resuscitating with a bag and mask	12	24	19.5 (81.3)	18.2 (75.8)	19.0 (79.2)	20.8 (86.7)
If baby is breathing	4	8	6.7 (83.8)	6.9 (86.3)	6.5 (81.3)	6.7 (83.8)
After 20mins, if baby does NOT begin breathing, heart rate is less than 60bpm, or if there is intercostal retraction or grunting	10	20	14.5 (72.5)	14.3 (71.5)	14.5 (72.5)	14.6 (73.0)
Post resuscitation management	12	24	21.4 (89.2)	19.8 (82.5)	22.6 (94.2)	21.7 (90.4)
Post-procedure tasks	4	8	6.8 (85.0)	6.1 (76.3)	7.2 (90.0)	7.0 (87.5)

Overall	92	184	152.6 (82.9)	141.2 (76.7)	156.3 (84.9)	158.9 (86.4)
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Table 4.3.1 shows the knowledge of perinatal asphyxia management among healthcare providers by facility level. The components that were assessed include: basic equipment and medications required for the management of perinatal asphyxia, preparation for the management, diagnosing a newborn with preinatal asphyxia, preliminary steps in the management, provision of warmth, tactile stimulation, bag and mask ventilation, post resuscitation management and post-procedural tasks. The mean score across the facilities ranged between 72.5%-92.8% while the overall score in all the components for all the facilities was 82.9%. On the whole, primary level facilities had the lowest score of 76.7% whereas the highest score of 86.4% was obtained by the tertiary level facilities.

Figure 4.4: Overall Knowledge of Healthcare Providers on the Management of PA

Figure 4.4 above shows the overall knowledge of the healthcare providers on the management of PA. Healthcare providers in the primary health facilities were observed to have the lowest score which is within the 'poor knowledge' category. The knowledge scores of healthcare providers in the secondary and tertiary facilities fell within the good category while those working in tertiary health facilities had the highest average score in the three facility levels.

Figure 4.5: Knowledge Scores of Healthcare Providers based on Job Category

Figure 4.5 above presents the percentage distribution of knowledge scores of healthcare providers by job category. The results showed that majority (70.9%) of nurses with specialization followed by 66.7% of general nurses, 53.8% medical officer with specialization, 47.4% medical officer and 27.3% community health workers had good knowledge in managing perinatal asphyxia.

4.6: Knowledge score for all Respondents

Across all levels, more than half (57.1%) of respondents had good knowledge while 42.9% had poor knowledge of perinatal asphyxia management (Figure 4.6).

4.4 Facility Readiness for the Management of PA

Table 4.4.1 Availability of Skilled Birth Attendants

Table 4.4.1 above shows the availability of skilled birth attendants in the selected health facilities. In all the primary health facilities, there were no gynecologists,

Facility	Gynecologist	Pediatrician	Anesthesiologist	Medical Officer	Nurse	Pediatric Nurse	Nurse Anesthetist	Midwife	Total	Score (%)
Enuwa	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	2	2.5	21.7
Arubiewe	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2.5	21.7
Okeamola	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0.5	4.3
Akinorun	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	2	2.5	21.7
Isokun	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	1	1.5	13.0
Irebami	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0.5	4.3
Atelewo	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	3	3.5	30.4
OkaBaale	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	3	3.5	30.4
Oke Gada	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0.5	4.3
OjaTimi	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	2	3.5	30.4
Alaye	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	1.5	13.0
Ikoyi	0	0	0	0.5	1	0	0	0	1.5	13.0
Mean of PF	0	0	0	0.5	0.3	0	0	1.2	2	17.35
Asubiaro	0	0	0	5	2	0	3	9	19	82.6
Ede	0	0	0	5	0	0	3	7	15	65.2
Ilesa	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	4	9	39.1
Iwo	2	0	0	2	0	0	1	6	11	47.8
Ikirun	0	0	0	4	0	0	2	6	12	52.2
Ife	0	0	0	3	4	0	1	3	11	47.8
Mean of SF	0	0	0	3.8	1	0	1.8	5.8	12.8	55.8
OAU (Labour Ward)	4	2	2	3	0	0	2	19	32	100
OAU (NICU)	0	6	2	1	0	10	0	4	23	100
LTH(Labour Ward)	4	2	1	1	0	0	1	15	24	100
LTH (NICU)	0	4	1	1	0	3	0	11	20	87
Mean of TF	2	3.5	1.5	1.5	0	3.2	0.8	12.2	22.3	96.8

pediatricians, anesthesiologists, nurse anesthetists and pediatric nurses; medical

officers were only available based on request (called when there is an emergency); there was neither a nurse nor a midwife in about one-quarter (25%); while only a pediatric nurse was found to be available. Similarly in the secondary health facilities, there was neither a pediatrician nor a pediatric nurse, no anesthesiologists but there was at least one anesthetic nurse in each facility; physicians available were only medical officers, no gynecologists; while the other skilled health providers available were either nurses or midwives.

Table 4.4.2 Readiness of Healthcare Providers for the Management of PA

Personnel variable	Primary (%)	Secondary (%)	Tertiary (%)	Mean
Density	17.4	55.8	96.8	56.7
Knowledge	76.7	84.9	86.4	82.7
In-service training	6.8	12.8	26.8	15.5
Overall	33.6	51.2	70	51.6

Table 4.3 above shows the core healthcare providers that were available for management of PA. The components of availability that were assessed include density, knowledge and in-service training. The density of core healthcare providers was found to be abysmally low in the primary level facilities with a score of 17.4% meanwhile, the density was observed to be highest in the tertiary level facilities with a score of 100%. Generally, healthcare providers were found to be lacking in in-service with only 6.8%, 12.8% and 26.8% found to have received a recent update in the management of PA in the selected primary, secondary and tertiary health facilities respectively Overall, the availability score observed in primary level facilities was less half of each of the scores obtained in secondary and tertiary levels where the availability scores were 64.5% and 71.1% respectively.

Table 4.4.3: Basic Equipment Available for the Management of PA

Basic equipment	Primary n=12 (%)	Secondary n=6 (%)	Tertiary n=4 (%)
Infant ambu bag	4 (33.3)	5(83.3)	4 (100)
Face mask (size 0)	4 (33.3)	4 (66.7)	4 (100)
Face mask (size 1)	6 (50)	4 (66.7)	4 (100)
Stethoscope	8 (66.7)	6(100)	4 (100)
Bulb syringe/Mucus extractor/Suctioning machine	6(50)	5(83.3)	4 (100)
Pre-warmed towels/Resuscitaire	0 (0)	1(16.7)	2 (50)
Newborn resuscitation table	3 (25)	4 (66.7)	2 (50)
Clock with seconds	6 (50)	4 (66.7)	3 (75)
Overall	38.5	68.7	84.4

Regarding basic equipment for management of PA, table 4.4 above shows that none of the three levels of selected health facilities had all the basic equipment required for the management of newborns with PA. Similarly, pre-warmed towels were not available in any of the selected facilities but about half of the tertiary health facilities have resuscitaires. All the facilities in the primary level do not have resuscitaires while it was only observed to be available in one (16.7%) secondary health facility. Newborn resuscitation tables and infant ambu bags were least available in the primary health facility level with scores of 25% and 33.3% (respectively). All the tertiary health facilities have infant ambu bags, face masks (size 0), face masks (size 1), stethoscope and bulb syringe (and or suctioning machine), whereas in the secondary facilities only stethoscope was found to be general while infant ambu bags, face masks (size 1), face masks (size 0) and bulb syringe (and or suctioning machine) had availability scores of 83.3%, 66.7%, 66.7% and 83.3% (respectively). Finally, clock with second hands was found to be available in half (50%), two-third (66.7%) and three-quarter (75%) of the selected primary, secondary and tertiary

facilities, in that order.

Table 4.4.5: Availability of Essential Medications for the Management of PA

Medications	Facility Level			
	Primary (%)	Secondary (%)	Tertiary (%)	All (N=20)
0.9% Normal saline				
Not available	1 (8.3)	3 (50.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (18.2)
Available	11 (91.7)	0 (0.0)	2 (50.0)	13 (59.1)
Available but procured out of pocket	0 (0.0)	3 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	5 (22.7)
10% Dextrose water				
Not available	1 (8.3)	3 (50.0)	1 (25.0)	5 (22.7)
Available	11 (91.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	12 (54.6)
Available but procured out of pocket	0 (0.0)	3 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	2 (22.7)
1:10000 epinephrine				
Not available	12 (100.0)	6 (100.0)	2 (50.0)	20 (91.0)
Available	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	1 (4.5)
Available but procured out of pocket	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	1 (4.5)
Phenobarbitone				
Not available	12 (100.0)	5 (83.3)	2 (50.0)	19 (86.4)
Available	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	1 (4.6)
Available but procured out of pocket	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	1 (25.0)	2 (9.0)
Whole blood				
Not available	12 (100.0)	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	18 (81.8)
Available	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)	0 (0.0)

Table 4.4.4 indicates that whole blood and 1:10000 epinephrine were not available in all the primary and secondary health facilities; whole blood was available in the 4 units (100%) of the tertiary facilities while 1:10000 epinephrine was provided by the government in only one-quarter (25%) of the units, one-quarter (25%) were provided out of pocket and the remaining half (50%) do not have it at all. None (0%) of the primary health facilities had phenobarbitone, it has to be procured out of pocket in the only (16.7%) secondary facility where it was available, while in the tertiary facilities, half (50%) do not have it, one quarter (25%) have it procured by the government and in the remaining one quarter (25%), it has to be procured out of pocket. Volume expanders (0.9% normal saline and 10% dextrose water) were not available in half (50%) and about 8.3% of the selected secondary and primary health facilities respectively; whereas in the tertiary facilities, 10% dextrose water was not available in 25% and procured out of pocket in half (50%); while 0.9% normal saline is only available in half (50%) and has to be procured out of pocket in the remaining half (50%).

Table 4.4.5: Basic Amenities for the Management of PA

Infrastructure	Primary n=12 (%)	Secondary n=6 (%)	Tertiary n=4 (%)	Mean
Phone	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (50.0)	16.7
Newborn care corner	0 (0.0)	1 (16.7)	4 (100.0)	38.9
Ambulance	1 (8.3)	3 (50.0)	4 (100.0)	52.8
Backup power supply	0 (0.0)	2 (33.3)	4 (100.0)	44.4
Water supply	6 (50.0)	6 (100.0)	4 (100.0)	83.3
Mean	11.7	40.0	90.0	

Table 4.4.5 above presents the availability of infrastructure in the selected facilities. For all the components assessed, 8.3% and 50% of the primary level facilities had an ambulance (functional and fueled) and regular supply of water as at the time of the study, all the other components of infrastructure were not available. Although only half (50%) of the tertiary level facilities had a cellular phone for communication, all the other components were present. Also as presented in the table, none of the secondary level had a cellular phone; 16.7% had a newborn care corner; 33.3%, backup power supply; 50%, ambulance; while all (100%) have a regular supply of water.

Table 4.4.6: Overall Readiness of Health Facilities

Facility Level	Infrastructure (%)	Guideline (%)	Personnel (%)	Equipment (%)	Facility Level Average (%)
Primary	11.7	0	31.7	38.4	20.45
Secondary	40.0	0	64.5	66.2	42.675
Tertiary	90.0	25	71.1	58.3	61.1
Mean for all Levels	47.2	8.3	55.8	52.5	40.95

Table 4.4.6 above presents the overall readiness of the facility levels based on the mean availability of service-specific tracer items in these domains: staff and training, equipment, medicines and commodities. Domains with scores less than 50% are marked red; those between 51% and 74% were marked yellow; while those above

75% are marked green.

4.5: Barriers to the Management of Newborns with PA

Table 4.5: Results of Quantitative Study on the Barriers to the Management of PA

Facility-related factors	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Poor infrastructure for perinatal asphyxia management	104 (66.4)	44 (28.4)	8 (5.2)	0 (0.0)
Deficient equipment supply or repair	106 (67.7)	45 (29.0)	5 (3.2)	0 (0.0)
Failure to replenish out of stock supplies and medications	106 (67.7)	42 (27.1)	8 (5.2)	0 (0.0)
Facility layout that supports newborn resuscitation	106 (68.4)	39 (25.2)	8 (5.2)	2 (1.2)
Inadequate human resources for newborn resuscitation	107 (68.4)	35 (22.6)	14 (9.0)	0 (0.0)

Corruption among healthcare providers	78 (49.7)	34 (21.9)	43 (27.7)	1 ((0.7)
Poor Doctor-Nurse relationship	94 (60.0)	42 (27.1)	17 (10.9)	3 (1.9)
Lack/low facility sponsored in-service training	110 (70.3)	42 (27.1)	4 (2.6)	0 (0.0)
Lack/low facility sponsored refresher training	109 (69.7)	39 (25.2)	8 (5.1)	0 (0.0)
No/low mentoring/modeling in newborn resuscitation	94 (60.0)	45 (29.0)	15 (9.7)	2 (1.3)
Absence of guideline/flowchart for management of PA in the delivery room	97 (61.9)	44 (28.4)	13 (8.4)	2 (1.3)
Lack of team approach during the management of PA	94 (60.0)	45 (29.0)	16 (10.3)	1 (0.7)
Lack/ineffective supervision and feedback	88 (56.1)	49 (31.6)	19 (12.3)	0 (0.0)
Lack of skill stations or simulations	84 (53.6)	49 (31.6)	22 (14.2)	1 (0.6)
No perinatal mortality audits	92 (58.7)	24 (15.5)	34 (21.9)	6 (3.9)
Poor staff performance evaluation	92 (58.7)	33 (21.3)	29 (18.7)	2 (1.3)
No pre-service training in the basic management of PA	96 (61.3)	37 (23.9)	23 (14.8)	0 (0.0)
Poor skills in PMA among healthcare providers	94 (60.0)	51 (32.9)	11 (7.1)	0 (0.0)
Low level of confidence among healthcare providers	91 (58.0)	37 (23.9)	27 (17.4)	1 (0.7)
Poor mentor-mentee relationship	90 (57.4)	47 (30.3)	15 (9.7)	4 (2.6)
Long-term use of non-evidence based practice	93 (59.4)	37 (23.9)	25 (16.1)	1 (0.6)
Resistance to change	81 (51.6)	41 (26.4)	32 (20.7)	2 (1.3)
Ineffective communication during the procedure	82 (52.3)	38 (24.5)	33 (21.3)	3 (1.9)
Poor documenting intervention	91 (58.0)	37 (23.9)	24 (15.5)	4 (2.6)
Poor use of delivery registers	82 (52.3)	32 (20.7)	37 (23.9)	5 (3.2)
Low number of perinatal asphyxia that have been previously managed by the provider	92 (58.7)	33 (21.3)	27 (17.4)	4 (2.6)

*SA=strongly agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=strongly disagree

As shown in table 4.7 above, respondents identified some of the barriers to the management of newborns with perinatal asphyxia. Majority of the factors identified are intra-personal, interpersonal and inter-professional factors on the part of the healthcare providers that grossly affect their ability to manage newborn babies with perinatal asphyxia. Furthermore, some facility related factors as well as government related factors were identified by the participants.

About two-third (66.4%, 67.7% and 67.7% respectively) of the participants strongly agreed that poor infrastructure, deficient supply of equipment, failure to replenish out of stock supplies and medications constitute barriers to the management of PA while none of them strongly disagreed with this opinion. Similarly, almost the same population (68.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed that lack of facility layout that supports management of PA and inadequate human resources also constitutes barrier to the management of PA.

Regarding healthcare providers related factors, almost half (49.7) of the respondents strongly agreed that corruption among healthcare providers is a barrier to the management of PA. Similarly, about two-third (60%) of them are of a strong opinion that poor doctor-nurse relationship, no/low mentoring, lack of team approach during management of PA and poor skills in perinatal asphyxia management also constitute up barriers to the management of PA.

4.5.2: Results from Qualitative Study

The theory of human behavior was adapted to develop theoretical insight into the respondents' perception of barriers to the management of PA. This theory was

adopted because it provides interpretation for the antecedents to healthcare providers' ability to manage newborns with PA in the selected health facilities.

The qualitative aspect of this study involved the use of an in-depth interview guide to explore the factors that participants perceived to constitute barriers to the management of PA in their facilities. At the end of the analysis of the responses of the participants, four themes emerged: (i) healthcare providers' related barriers; (ii) parents' related factors; (iii) facility related barriers; and (iv) government related factors.

Figure 4.7: Themes and Sub-Themes from Interview

4.5.2.1 Healthcare Providers' Related Barriers

The respondents communicated different factors that relate to the healthcare providers which affect their ability to manage newborns with perinatal asphyxia

effectively. Some of these factors include the knowledge and in-service training of healthcare providers, attitude, supervision and mentoring for the management of PA.

Knowledge, In-service training and update

The respondents recounted that regular training is very essential to sustain the skills and improve the abilities of healthcare providers in the management of PA. According to them, the knowledge of a large number of the healthcare providers is at the low ebb because most of them are relying on the basic training they received during the basic education for their job category as the only source of knowledge for the management of PA.

“...for most of the healthcare providers the skill is not there and you can't give what you don't have. Many people have stopped learning, they are practicing what they were taught in school about 15-20 years ago so there is knowledge deficit. It is not that they don't know it, but it's not at the tip of their fingers because this is not a condition that happens every day. It is an emergency that happens once in a while but it needs perfect readiness and skillful service...” [Female, 37 years].

This submission is in consonance with the results obtained in a study by Fikre and Fiche, (2018) where it was observed that healthcare providers who had training in newborn care were 4 times knowledgeable when compared to others who did not have this training. Acharya and Paudel (2015) therefore concluded that upgrading the knowledge of healthcare providers in newborn care should be given greater emphasis in order to improve their health outcome. Availability of equipment alone

in health facilities is worth almost nothing if care providers lack the capacity to use it. Administrators and managers of health facilities need to make provision for continuous education including booster trainings for healthcare providers working in labour and newborn care units in order to keep them abreast with current trends in the management of asphyxiated newborns.

Worse still, one of the respondents who belonged to the CHP job category said that her category of healthcare providers do not even have any basic training for the management of PA.

"...most health providers, especially in primary health care, we are not good in managing perinatal asphyxia because most community health practitioners are not trained for that, we are mostly trained for immunization..." [Female, 42 years].

Attitude of healthcare providers

This study also found that attitude of healthcare providers could be a barrier to the management of newborns with asphyxia. The negative attitudes were however reported by the participants to be due to some facility and government related factors like lack of material and human resources that culminate in burnout among the healthcare providers. For example, inadequate human resources result in increased workload and increased working hours of the healthcare providers.

"...I can easily go to the emergency tray and pick up the things I need, it makes life easy for me, I don't get frustrated, I don't get worked up. If I need to walk for or look for phenobarbitone for almost 20 minutes seeing a child that is

convulsing, it's, I get discouraged..." [Male, 38 years].

Mentoring and supervision

The participants identified the fact that mentoring improves the skills of freshly appointed healthcare providers as well as supervision. As noted by two of the participants, healthcare providers whose skills are not sharpened in the management of PA will have the opportunity of learning current skills from those who have updated knowledge. Also, they will have the opportunity of receiving corrections and mastering the right set of skills during supervision sessions and watching regular sessions that are either practiced or simulated by mentors. It was pointed by participants that mentoring and supervision are currently lacking in the health facilities where this study was conducted.

"...So in terms of the mentoring and supervision, to be sincere and to be candid, we don't have such. There is nothing like mentoring, there is nothing like supervision. Even you will see a newly employed midwife or nurse that will be carrying out a procedure without supervision; you will see a newly appointed house officer carrying out a procedure, without supervision. So what do you expect from, from do you expect from that kind of ah ah procedure So we are lacking that two, two major phenomenon of mentoring and supervision" [Female, 34 years].

4.5.2.2 Parents Related Factors

Other factors that participants opined to constitute barriers to the management of PA are related to parents of the newborns that are affected. Some of these factors

are connected to lack of funds and health seeking behaviours of such parents. These sometimes have a direct influence on their ability make choices that could have salvaged the newborn from developing the condition, procure medications and other supplies that will be required to manage the newborn or accept medical advices that will save the newborn from the long term sequelae that are associated with the condition. The parent-related factors that were identified by the participants include:

Inability of patients to procure required medications due to poverty

The high poverty level among people living in this part of the world has a resultant effect on their health and health choices. As noted by some of the participants, lack of fund on the side of the parents prevent them from making available the essential drugs that will be required to manage the newborns, especially when they are not available at the facility pharmacy or when they have to procure them out their own pockets. When these drugs and supplies are not available, healthcare providers will not be able to successfully manage newborns with perinatal asphyxia. Some of them commented as follows:

"...and our challenges is this: most of these patients cannot afford to buy these injection hydrocortisone, adrenaline, needle and syringe; even they don't know, some they don't know what to eat in the evening, so they cannot afford to buy pad, to buy glove.. So some are living in penury, they are living in

poverty..." [Female, 42 years].

Patients refusing referral for management in another facility with better resources

One of the participants noted that when there is a need to refer the newborn for better management, the parents may refuse either due to the fact that the better resources will infer extra or higher costs or because of the fear that the baby may ultimately not make it even after spending so much.

".. At a stage, thank God we can, with the stethoscope, ehm, stethoscope, we can pick the heart rate, but still, you know, usually, you want the baby to cry, because to to to, because of the oxygen depletion to the brain. So everybody were worried, we were thinking, even we were telling the mother that we were referring this baby out, but the mother said no, you know, the mother is a learned somebody. So she knew that probably this baby will not make it 'jare', let me just leave this baby. But we were all worried and said, even we were even planning to refer that baby, the mother said no" [Female, 57].

Delay in seeking medical attention during labour

Another important factor that was raised by one of the participant was the factor that makes the management of PA difficult is the fact that some of the patients in labour do not present early enough. This poses a major challenge because it becomes difficult for the healthcare provider attending to the delivery to make adequate preparation for the team of personnel that would be necessary to attend to the delivery should this baby need extra care or present with an emergency after birth. This further delays the time available for the newborn to receive prompt intervention and could worsen the complications associated with the condition.

“...Then government also need to, maybe in the television in everything, they need to make eh, make eh, let the people know that they should not delay the.. eh when they, the time they fall to labour, they should not delay themselves, they should come to the health facility at the normal at appropriate time...” [Female, 46 years].

Unwillingness of Patients to accept alternative birth options

Similarly, it was discovered during this study that when some patients are presented with alternative birth options to hasten the time of delivery and avert possible complications that may result to stress of the baby in-utero, they are often not willing to accept those options for reasons ranging from lack of fund, fear of stigmatization and cultural believes about such alternatives. This will usually have a resultant effect on the baby and make the management of asphyxia management difficult due to elongated time lag.

“...a woman that is managed in my facility, if we are able to manage the case well, we don't usually have a case like that, unless those you know, by the time you are counseling them this baby need CS you know, they are causing a lot of delay, and when you want to refer them, they will tell you they're not going, and you know, you can't push out your patient. We had a case like that last week, we were even begging her let's do CS, you know, she was very reluctant, you know the stigma that people attach to it” [Female, 57 years].

4.5.2.3 Facility Related Factors

Participants further identified some factors that are associated with the facilities

which impair their abilities to manage PA. These factors characterize the facilities where newborns with perinatal asphyxia are being managed.

Equipment and supplies

It was observed during this study that majority of the health facilities do not have all the basic equipment required for the management of PA. The equipment were often observed not to be available or not functional. This has greatly hindered the healthcare providers from managing newborns with perinatal asphyxia. An example is a situation where a newborn needs oxygen to augment its own supply and there is no oxygen cylinder or the cylinder is empty. A persistent deficiency in the supply of oxygen to the brain makes the management more difficult for the healthcare providers. Lack of equipment to work with also reduces the frequency of management and the skills of healthcare providers in the management of PA.

“One major obstacle is lack of equipment, like in this facility there is no facemask for the neonate, no oxygen cylinder, nothing Even if we have, I’m sure it would have been empty by now. There is nothing and nobody wants to be responsible for it. Most of the time I have personally written proposals and it has yielded nothing, nothing would be done...” [Female, 37 years].

46years].

This finding is similar to that Kamenir, (1997). This results in poor practices, including errors in sequencing of care, such as delays in initiating positive pressure ventilation (PPV); provision of chest compressions before or without establishing an airway and ventilator support; and administering drugs before PPV (Mitchell et al, 2002). In a similar study, Wagner (2015) observed that frequent unavailability of

resuscitation materials in delivery rooms led to delays in initiating resuscitation when managing a newborn with PA

Lack of guideline/protocols for resuscitation

According to one of the participants, the presence of newborn resuscitation protocol in the labour room or resuscitation area will keep the healthcare providers abreast of the steps involved in the management of PA. However, it was discovered that the protocol was only available in one of the facilities.

"...Then in terms of protocols, the facility does not have a protocol, that is the truth. The facility does not have a protocol to follow when you want to manage perinatal asphyxia, there is no protocol. Because all those protocols are supposed to be there and even pasted where you can see it. Sometimes, when it seems you want to forget what you should do, you can even glance through the chart, that one is not there..." [Female, 41 years].

Prolonged decision-to-incision time frame

One of the respondents noted that facility protocol often cause a delay between the time a decision is made for a cesarean birth and the actual incision time. According to her, this often results in poor outcomes in the newborns.

"... for the protocol in this hospital, the main problem we have in this hospital is when you need to do emergency cesarean section, and you have to inform the anaesthetists, you have the PONs, you inform this, you inform that, before

the.. Sometimes, the decision time and the incision time is very very long. To me, I don't think the decision and the decision time should be more than 30minutes is even long..." (Female, 38 years)

This finding is supported by Fahey (2014) who reported that fetuses with bradycardia prior to birth often present with better outcomes when they are born quickly. She further recommended that as soon as a decision to proceed on a cesarean birth has been made, undue delays in preparations to implement the intervention should be avoided.

4.5.2.4 Government Related Factors

Participants also discussed the part that the government should wade in especially where the facilities and the healthcare providers do not have the capacity to proffer solutions for such deficiencies. They lamented that the chronic inadequacies of human resources and other facilities have an immense impact on the management of perrinatal asphyxia. Some of the factors that were identified include the following:

Human resources

According to the submission of most of the participants, there is a gross deficiency in the human resources available in all the health facilities. This has resulted in unavailability (reduced) of essential healthcare providers when there is a need to manage newborns with perinatal asphyxia. Similarly, this deficiency means that healthcare providers will have to work for more hours than is required, suffer burnout

and a reduction in their efficiency and capacity to manage newborns with perinatal asphyxia.

"...Look at the situation of things now in Osun State, we are operating two shifts, which is not supposed to be you must have morning, afternoon and night. But the person that work from the 8 (am) till 6 (pm); even gan that 6 (pm) at times may be 7 (pm) due to the delay of the other eh eh.., so they are over, we are over labour, so they over labour us here..." [Female, 46 years].

Transportation

An ambulance is required to transport an asphyxiated neonate in order to ensure continuous management, safety during the course of transportation and improves the speed of transfer to the point where s/he will be better managed. However, participants recounted their painful experiences they had when there was a need to transfer asphyxiated newborns. The transfer was either impossible or terribly delayed due to unavailability of an ambulance in the health facility or fuel in the ambulance, thereby increasing the chances of these newborns developing long term sequelae that may result.

"...By the time the baby was brought out, just to manage it, even the husband was saying ha mummy, are you going to refer us? I 'ni' no, don't worry, it's what we can manage, so don't bother. But in one, for one reason or the other, they should go and get a vehicle ready for me and said okay, no proble,.. so the vehicle was not working again, so I had to tell them please, go and get us okada. There's one man around us, and one of the community leader, so he now give us okada. I mow carry the baby on my back at that 1a.m." [Female,

44 years].

Water supply

One of the participants reported that was no water source to supply the sanitary needs during perinatal asphyxia management within the facility. She said that staff members from the hospital usually go in search of water within the neighbourhood in order to meet the need of the health facility.

"...We don't have water, we do go outside there to fetch water. ; we need ehn portable water, especially ehn, pipe borne water..." [Female, 42 years].

Power supply

Participants reported lack and inadequacy of backup for power source when electric power supply ceases. This sometimes prevents the healthcare providers from powering the equipment that are required for the management of newborns with perinatal asphyxia. Examples of such equipment include resuscitaires and suctioning machines.

"..there was a situation where we have to take a resuscitation machine to the labour ward and there was no light, no electricity to power the suction machine. So at the end of the day, something bad happened. So, lack of regular supply of electricity is a problem, because government is the one that is supposed to provide that..." [Female, 41 years].

Poor hospital structure

The study found that the structure of health facilities also constitute barrier to the

management of PA. The major challenges that were reported by the participants range from too much ventilation than is required for a newborn with asphyxia, dilapidated structures, lack of newborn care corners to long distance of delivery room from resuscitation area. Some of the participants have these to say about how the structures of their facilities affect their ability to manage newborns with perinatal asphyxia:

"Factors that influence the practice of care providers: most of them are not motivated, the hospital setting and environment are nothing to write home about, most settings have buildings/structures that are dilapidated, when some are coming to the hospital you see on their faces that they are not happy with the environment they are coming to.. [Female 37years]

Hmm, well, let me start from the structure of the health facility. Hmm, normally, you know, we have different types of eh different rooms at the eh, when you talk about the eh, eh, labour room, so, it's not well structured because we need to consider the babies...Because like this one now, we have labour room and antenatal together. Assuming that we want to do palpation now, there's no, eh, which is not, we have to use that place no enough space for us, hmm. So assuming that we don't have the delivery, we clean it and use the second couch that we normally use. It's not suppose to be there, like that. We should have the palpation room difference, then the labour room" [Female, 46 years]

4.6 Testing of Hypotheses

Table 4.6.1: Binary logistic regression showing relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and healthcare providers' knowledge on Perinatal Asphyxia Management

Variables	Odds ratio	p-value	95%CI
Age (in years)			
20 – 29	RC	RC	RC
30 – 39	1.371	0.506	0.540 – 3.478
40 – 49	0.741	0.529	0.291 – 1.884
50 and above	1.485	0.515	0.452 – 4.893
Marital status			
Single	RC	RC	RC
Married	1.877	0.186	0.733 – 4.766
Widowed	5.333	0.164	0.506 – 6.236
Job category			
General Nurses	RC	RC	RC
Nurse with Specialization	1.217	0.766	0.335 – 4.443
Medical Officer	0.450	0.297	0.100 – 2.018
Medical Officer with Specialization	0.583	0.515	0.115 – 2.952
Community Health Practitioners	0.188	0.021*	0.045 - 0.779
Ward or unit			
Labor ward	RC	RC	RC
Maternity	0.917	0.819	0.435 – 1.934
Newborn	4.667	0.004*	1.626 – 13.393
Theater	2.500	0.302	0.439 – 14.225
Facility level			
Primary	RC	RC	RC
Secondary	2.989	0.011*	1.284 – 6.961
Tertiary	4.706	0.000*	2.108 – 10.505
Management of PA			
No	RC	RC	RC
Yes	1.800	0.153	0.804 – 4.031
Received supervision			
No	RC	RC	RC
Yes	1.435	0.274	0.751 – 2.741
Year of experience			
1 – 5	RC	RC	RC
6 – 10	1.808	0.224	0.695 – 4.701
11 – 15	1.230	0.672	0.472 – 3.209
16 – 20	0.721	0.555	0.244 – 2.133
21 – 25	1.875	0.337	0.519 – 6.770

*significant at 0.05% confidence interval

The results from the binary logistic regression to examine the relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and their knowledge on management of PA are presented in Table 4.6.1 above. For age, marital status, supervision and years of experience, results show that there was no significant association. Similarly in the results, being in the age groups of 23-39 (1.371) and 50 and above (1.485); being single (1.877) and married (5.333), having in-service training of management of PA(2.762), and receiving supervision (1.435) were all observed to increase the odds of the participants having good knowledge on management of PA with no statistical significance between the variables. It is evident from these results that there is no statistically significant relationship between knowledge score among healthcare providers and their years of experience. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant association between the years of experience of healthcare providers and their knowledge on management of PA was accepted ($p=0.023$).

As further revealed, nurses with specialization (1.217) have an increased odds of having good knowledge while the respondents that were medical officers (0.450), medical officers with specialization (0.583), community health practitioners job (0.188) have reduced odds of having good knowledge. The community health practitioner job category was statistically significant with good knowledge on management of PA at a value of 0.021 significant at 95% confidence interval. The table also illustrated that working in newborn unit (4.667) increased the odds of the respondents having good knowledge, significantly associated with knowledge on

management of PA at a value of 0.021 at 95% confidence interval.

Similarly, working in the secondary and tertiary facility levels was significantly associated with knowledge on management of PA at values of 0.011 and 0.000 respectively, significant at 95% confidence interval. Working in the secondary and tertiary facility level was also observed to significantly increase the odds of the participants having knowledge on management of PA but were not statistically significant with having knowledge on management of PA. Consequent to the significant associations between knowledge and facility ($p=0.011$; 0.001) for secondary and tertiary levels, the hypothesis for facility level was therefore rejected.

Table 4.6.2: Correlation Results Showing the Extent of Relationship between Respondents Year of Experience and Knowledge Scores

	Year of experience	Knowledge score
Year of experience		
Pearson Correlation	1	-0.071
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.379
Knowledge score		
Pearson Correlation	-0.071	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.379	

** Significant at 95% confidence level*

Table 4.6.2 showed that there exist a weak and inverse relationships between year of experience and knowledge score among the respondents. The correlation coefficient of respondents' year of experience and knowledge is negatively related. The result further revealed that there exists no statistically significant association between year of experience and knowledge score.

Table 4.6.3: ANOVA Results Showing Mean Difference Respondents Knowledge Score by Job Category

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	8901.50	4	2225.38	8.41	0.000*
Within Groups	39942.67	151	264.52		
Total	48844.17	155	315.12		

** Significant at 95% confidence level*

Table 4.6.3 shows analysis of results whether there is statistically significant difference between the group means. It can be observed that the significance value is 0.000 ($p=0.000$), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, there is statistically significant difference in the mean of job category.

Table 4.6.4: ANOVA Results Showing Mean Difference in Respondents Knowledge Score and Facility Level.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	9448.21	2	4724.10	18.35	0.000*
Within Groups	39844.96	153	257.49		
Total	48844.17	155	315.12		

** Significant at 95% confidence level*

Table 4.6.4 shows analysis of variance results whether there is statistically significant difference between the group means. It can be observed that the significance value is 0.000 ($p=0.000$), which is less than 0.05. Therefore, there is statistically significant difference in the mean of facility level.

Table 4.6.5: Distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of job category

Job category	Poor	Good	χ^2	p-value
General Nurses	4 (33.3)	8 (66.7)	19.348	0.001*
Nurse with Specialization	23 (29.1)	56 (70.9)		
Medical Officer	10 (52.6)	9 (47.4)		
Medical Officer with Specialization	6 (46.2)	7 (53.8)		
Community Health Practitioners	24 (72.7)	9 (27.3)		

**significant at 0.05% confidence interval*

Table 4.6.5 shows the distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of job category. The results showed that the job categories were significantly associated with knowledge score with a value of 0.001 at 95% confidence interval.

Table 4.6.6: Distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of Facility level

Facility level	Poor	Good	χ^2	p-value
Primary	32 (65.3)	17 (34.7)	15.645	0.000*
Secondary	17 (38.6)	27 (61.4)		
Tertiary	18 (28.6)	45 (71.4)		

**significant at 0.05% confidence interval*

Table 4.6.6 shows the distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of facility level. The results showed that facility level had a statistically significant association with knowledge score with a value of 0.000 at 95% confidence interval.

Table 4.6.7: Distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of working units

Working unit	Poor	Good	χ^2	p-value
Labor ward	23 (50.0)	23 (50.0)	12.804	0.005*
Maternity	36 (52.2)	33 (47.8)		
Newborn	6 (17.7)	28 (82.3)		
Theater	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)		

Table 4.6.7 shows the distribution of knowledge score among healthcare providers in terms of working units. The results showed that the working units had a statistically significant association with knowledge score with a value of 0.001 at 95% confidence interval.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

In this study, the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia, knowledge of healthcare providers and facility readiness for the management of PA were explored in selected health facilities in Osun State. In conformity with reviewed literature (Daniel, 2014; Daniel Muturi Gichogo et al., 2018; Danilel Muturi Gichogo, 2016), health facilities were in resource poor setting and therefore readiness for the management of PA was significantly low across the three levels of health facilities that were selected for this study. Finally, the barriers to healthcare providers ability to manage PA were found to be enormous and beyond the control of the providers across the three levels of health facilities.

The estimation of the prevalence of PA was essential to project the proportion of neonatal mortality that is due to PA in the State. The prevalence of PA was found to vary across the three facility levels and highest in the tertiary level of health facilities. It was also noted that healthcare providers' knowledge in the management of PA was suboptimal especially in the primary level. Furthermore, the readiness scores of

majority of the facilities were observed to be very low because they were less equipped to manage newborns with PA.

5.1 Respondents and Facilities Characteristics

The respondents for this study were healthcare providers working in the delivery rooms and special units where sick newborns are cared for in the selected health facilities. Majority of them were female Christian nurses, and the mean ages were 38.5 (SD=9.2) and 39.9 (SD=7.2) for the quantitative and qualitative aspects respectively. It was observed that the proportion of healthcare providers working in the tertiary facilities were highest when compared with the other two facility levels. The density of skilled birth attendants was lowest in the primary health facilities even though the highest number of deliveries takes place there. Healthcare providers working in the tertiary and secondary levels were predominantly nurses and midwives while the primary level was dominated by the community health workers job category. The health facilities that were selected for this are government owned hospitals in Osun State.

5.2 Prevalence of Perinatal Asphyxia in Selected Health Facilities in Osun State

Findings from reviewed literature have shown that the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia is highest in Sub-Saharan Africa when compared with other regions of the world (Kamau, 2018). This difference in prevalence has been reported by Debillon et al. (2018) to be due the variation in the socio-economic status of these regions of the world. The results of this study showed that the prevalence of PA is still high (12.7%), but this is however in contrast with the report of a study that was carried out in Ethiopia by Gebreheat et al. (2018) which showed a high prevalence rate of

22.1% in the selected general hospitals. Although this study's findings depict that there is a significant improvement when compared with the result obtained in a similar study in Port Harcourt, Nigeria by West and Opara (2013) where the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia was reported to be 29.4%, there is still a huge margin between it and the recommended prevalence stated in the SDGs that was meant to be achieved by all countries by the year 2020.

It was also observed during this study that the prevalence of PA in tertiary health facilities is higher than that of the secondary and primary health facilities. Although this may be attributed to the fact that the tertiary facilities are referral centers, one of the respondents said that the management of out-born neonates with PA is particularly challenging because of delay in accessing advanced management either due to delay in initiating referrals or delay during the course of transportation to the referral center. This often results in poor health outcomes for newborns with PA.

Similarly from this study, asphyxia was observed to be a major cause of neonatal admission in the special units designated for the care of newborns in the selected tertiary facilities, accounting for 18.5% of the total number of sick newborns. This is dissimilar to findings in previous studies conducted among neonates by Aliyu, Lawal, and Onankpa (2017); and Dalal and Bodar (2013) where it was reported that the prevalence rate among neonates admitted in selected tertiary facilities were about one quarter and one third in Kano State (Nigeria) and Pakistan respectively (as cited in Egharevba et al., 2018). It is equally at variance with a study conducted among admitted newborns in a tertiary institution in Nigeria where Egharevba, Kayode-Adedeji, and Alikah, (2018) reported that perinatal asphyxia accounted for only one

tenth of the total neonatal admission in Edo State.

The discrepancies in the values for the prevalence of PA may have its antecedence in poor evaluation of newborns at birth, lack of uniformity in the diagnostic criteria and unavailability of vital records. It was observed during this study that there was no record documenting precisely the specific standard for assessing APGAR scores; healthcare providers often base their evaluation on personal opinion of what appears to be a low or good score because of the subjective nature of some of the components of the APGAR score. In climes with enough resources abound, laboratory tests are usually done to confirm the diagnosis and severity of PA to ensure better outcomes and quality of care.

Similarly, the difference in the prevalence rates may also due to the time gap between the two studies. Previously, facility deliveries in Nigeria were reported to be lower than it is in recent times. This is in congruence with findings from a similar study carried out in Ethiopia by Gudayu (2017). Another factor that may be responsible for inter-country disparity in prevalence rate is the fact that most resource poor countries still rely solely on low APGAR score as the criteria for diagnosing asphyxia. It has however been documented that APGAR scores are poor predictors of acid-base status and thus are considered insufficient to predict complications in the newborn (Fahey, 2014)

Data for the estimation of the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia in the selected primary health facilities for this study were found to be deficient because the documentation in this setting was observed to be poor; the record of APGAR scores

was largely not available or improperly recorded. In some of the health facilities, delivery registers were often not completed, newborn's assessment record were sometimes lumped in the same document and some of the documents were observed to be missing. The documentation of APGAR score in primary health facilities in Osun State was observed to be frequently illegible, consequently necessitating the use of the ability of the newborn to cry at birth as the criterion for inclusion in the study.

Therefore, the estimate of perinatal asphyxia in Osun State should be interpreted with caution because the data collected for the diagnosis of perinatal asphyxia across the three levels of health facilities lack uniformity. This finding corroborates Komolafe, Irinoye, and Hanson's (2017) submission that data capture pattern among nurses who provide perinatal care is poor. The unavailability of timely, accurate and sufficient data to estimate the prevalence of perinatal asphyxia as well as the predisposing factors associated with PA may be part of the reasons for the persistence in the high rate of perinatal mortality in Nigeria.

5.3 Knowledge of Asphyxia Management among Healthcare Providers in the Selected Health Facilities

The management of PA depends on the severity of the condition. Meanwhile, empirical studies have confirmed that the availability of healthcare providers that are skilled in neonatal resuscitation at every delivery is one of the measures that effectively prevents deaths and complications that may arise from perinatal asphyxia (Basu, 2014; Munezero et al., 2018; Murila et al., 2012).

It was observed that majority of the respondents in this study knew the equipment and supplies that were required for basic resuscitation; however, most of them have poor knowledge of the medications that are required for the management of PA. Moreover, the overall knowledge of healthcare providers at the primary facility levels in the management of PA was observed to be the lowest. It was observed that working in secondary and tertiary facility levels increased participants' chances of having adequate knowledge in the management of PA. This is comparable to the findings from the study of Mzurikwo et al. (2018) where it was reported that healthcare providers working in hospitals are more likely to have adequate knowledge in the management of PA than those working in health centers.

Moreover, a greater percentage of healthcare providers in the CHEW category were observed to have inadequate knowledge in the management of PA compared to those in other job categories. This is congruent with findings from similar studies. For example, Acharya and Paudel (2015) reported that more than two third of the nurse-midwives that were assessed for critical knowledge on the provision of maternal and newborn care services in primary level facilities in Nepal had poor knowledge in newborn care. This may not be delineated from the fact that the management of newborns is not included in the basic training of this category of care providers as reported by one of the respondents and supported by Tuncbalp et al. (2015) in their commentary on the quality of care for pregnant women and newborns. In another study conducted by Alhassan et al. (2019) in Ghana, it was also observed that almost all the participants in the study had insufficient knowledge on neonatal resuscitation.

According to Young et al. (2013) in their study, three quarters of the doctors and well above three quarters of the midwives that were selected for the study felt very confident as far as their ability to perform newborn resuscitation is concerned. This is in disagreement with findings from this study. In this study, majority of the respondents reported lack confidence in their ability to manage newborns with PA. This was attributed to infrequent management of cases as most newborns that were observed to have complications were often transferred to tertiary facilities due to lack of resources in their own facility levels. The theory of planned behaviour proposed that confidence is an intrinsic factor in an individual that affects his/her ability to perform a given behavior (Ardalan et al., 2017). A feeling of lack of confidence has been reported to reduce healthcare providers' capacity and ultimately readiness to manage PA.

Furthermore, it was observed in this study that healthcare providers with specializations and those with recent training/updates have higher knowledge scores compared to others who do not. This is comparable with findings from previous studies. It has been documented in the literature that healthcare providers with longer years of experience, specialization and recent update on newborn care have adequate knowledge and better practice than their counterparts who do not (Mzurikwao et al., 2018). Majority of the respondents noted that regular in-service training is essential to keep them abreast of current practices in the management of PA.

5.4 Facility Readiness for the Management of PA

A Policy note (2018) on the medical and healthcare issues in Nigeria based on a

census by the federal ministry of health in 2005 provides an estimate of the percentage of facilities and number of personnel that are available at different facility levels across the nation. More than eighty-five percent of the total number of health facilities in Nigeria are primary health facilities, fourteen percent are secondary while the remaining less than one percent are tertiary. One local government has at least five primary health facilities, making this level the most accessible to the population and as a result have the highest delivery loads across the three health facility levels.

Results from this study shows that the readiness of health facilities in Osun State is dwindling at the lower ebb, skilled birth attendants are unremittingly inadequate, equipment and supplies are grossly lacking while most of the infrastructures are simply deficient for the management of neonates with PA.

For instance, none of the primary health facilities had a medical doctor working on a full time basis while all the nurses and midwives are only available during the morning shifts. Therefore most deliveries are often not attended by skilled health workers. Thus there is always a delay in the provision of care when there is an emergency.

It has been reported that pediatricians are not usually available in resource poor settings to attend to difficult deliveries that are emergencies (Basu, 2014). This study confirmed this affirmation as there were pediatricians in one tenth of the facilities that were selected for this study, only the two (tertiary) of the overall twenty facilities had pediatricians In resource poor settings where there is usually a shortage of pediatricians, it has been reported that nurses are usually the medical

staffs that are available to manage neonates with perinatal asphyxia. Findings from this study however revealed that there is a shortage of this category of medical professionals especially in the primary health facilities, where there was neither a nurse nor a midwife in about half of the selected facilities which are most accessible and utilized by pregnant women for labour and deliveries.

In all the selected primary and secondary health facilities, there are no pediatricians, gynecologists and anesthetists. A pediatric nurse was only available in one of the selected primary facilities with none in the secondary facilities. Anesthetic nurses were available based on request in the labour wards of the selected secondary and tertiary health facilities with none in the primary health facilities. All but one of the primary health facilities have no medical officer to attend to the deliveries.

Narayan (2016) argued that it is essential to include newborn resuscitation in the curriculum of training of healthcare providers during their basic (pre-service) program. A fall out of his stance is the fact that pre-service training potentially provides greater sustainability over time and has a dual advantage of reducing the cost as well as the extended periods off work that healthcare providers will need in order to undergo the training. Similarly, Basu (2014) also reported that trials have shown that basic training in neonatal care has the tendency to reduce neonatal mortality. Albeit, more than half of the healthcare providers attending to deliveries in the primary health facilities selected for this study are community health practitioners who are unskilled birth attendants that do not have any basic training in newborn care. A comparable observation was also reported in a previous study by Adegoke and Broek (2009).

This has posed a major barrier to improved neonatal outcomes especially in SSA where this inadequacy is predominant (Sumankuuro et al., 2018). Even though some of this category of healthcare providers have had a recent in-service training in newborn care, WHO (2008) has affirmed that trainings for unskilled healthcare providers have failed to reduce mortality and neonatal morality (by implication) as it lacked the ability to impact the critical thinking and decision making skills required in the labour room.

Malekzadeh, Erfanian, and Khadivzadeh (2015) in a study conducted to evaluate the skills of nursing and midwifery students on neonatal resuscitation reported that the skills of the students that were examined was lower than expected even while in training. It was observed that the overall score of the students in the initial steps of resuscitation was thirty eight percent while their score in positive pressure ventilation was just forty nine percent. Findings from a study conducted by Munezero et al. (2018) revealed that most (fifty three percent) of the respondents have no formal training on the management of PA and only less than ten percent of them have had a prior training in basic life support (BLS). Findings from this study conversely is at variance with these positions as it revealed that majority of healthcare providers working across the three levels of health facilities have not received any in-service training on the management of PA in the past two years.

It was inferred from this study that almost all the primary and secondary health facilities did not have all the basic equipment and supplies the management of PA. This is consistent with a study conducted in Ethiopia by Gobezie, Bailey, Keyes, Ruano, and Teklie (2019) on readiness to treat and factors associated with the

survival of newborns with breathing difficulties. Results from the study showed that more than one-quarter of the health facilities that were included in the study did not have newborn masks (size 0 or 1). This was observed to have resulted in low survival status of newborns with asphyxia. The study also noted that required resuscitation pack was found to be lacking in primary care facilities.

According to a standard specification by WHO, the most standard basic resuscitation device that is required to ventilate a newborn that weighs less than 5 kg is a bag with mask (World Health Organization, 2016). It is used to initiate ventilation in babies who do not start breathing after drying thoroughly and stimulation. According to WHO (2016), it is particularly important in low resource settings because it does not require additional power source or pressurized gas to function. It is further recommended that ventilation should be provided with the bag and mask at 40-60 breathes per minute to maintain a tidal volume that is required to achieve adequate gas exchange.

Reports from the assessment of available equipment in the selected health facilities for this study showed that infant ambu bag with masks was available in a ready to use condition in only one-eighth out of the selected primary health facilities while in the secondary healthy facilities, one-quarter have ambu bags and masks available in a ready to use condition in the labour room, one-eighth has it available in the theater, one-quarter have it available but dusty and the remaining one-eighth does not have it at all in the labour rooms. On the contrary, these values are incompatible with respondents' reported availability. The respondents reported a higher availability of equipment against the observed availability.

Overall, the highest score obtained for the availability of basic equipment for the management of PA in this study was 85.7%, and was only observed in the labour rooms of the two selected tertiary health facilities. None of the facilities was found to have all the essential equipment required for the management of PA. This is comparable to the result from a similar study in Kenya where thirty five percent of the selected hospitals had a range of 0%-83% on the availability scale and about only two percent of the health centers (primary) had all the essential equipment. The smaller health facilities face a significant challenge in the review of essential indicators that reflect a newborn's wellbeing due to unavailability of essential equipment like a clock with a second hand (Narayanan, 2016).

Supportive supervision is a process that promotes quality at all levels of the health system by strengthening relationships within the system, focusing on the identification and resolution of problems, and helping to optimize the allocation of resources, promoting high standards, teamwork, and better two-way communication (Marquez and Kean 2002). A cornerstone of supportive supervision is working with health staff to establish goals, monitor performance, identify and correct problems, and proactively improve the quality of service. Together, the supervisor and health workers identify and address weaknesses on the spot, thus preventing poor practices from becoming routine. Supervisory visits are also an opportunity to recognize good practices and help health workers to maintain their high-level of performance. Colleagues from the same facility carry out internal supervision within the facility. Supervision takes place during routine work, team meetings, and visits by external supervisors.

During supervision, there is observation of performance and comparison with standards; provision of corrective and supportive feedback on performance; discussion with clients; provision of technical updates or guidelines; onsite training; use of data and client input to identify opportunities for improvement; joint problem solving, follow-up on previously identified problems. After each session of supervision, a list of actions and decisions is prepared in collaboration with healthcare providers in the unit, there is a need to agree on the means by which the decisions are to be implemented, continuous monitoring and improvement of weak areas should be ensured, as well as a follow-up on problems that were highlighted during prior visits.

More than three-quarters of neonates that were referred from primary and secondary facilities to tertiary facilities within the State for advanced neonatal resuscitation were not transported with ambulance. It could be inferred therefore that these neonates did not receive any care during the period of transportation to the point of referral. This finding was corroborated by the result obtained in a study of neonatal transport practices in Ibadan, Nigeria. In their study, Abdulraheem, Tongo, Orimadegun, and Akinbami (2016) observed that only 4% of sick neonates who required better medical management were transported in an ambulance. It was noted in the study that while some neonates were transported on foot, other means of transportation include private vehicles, motorcycles, and private vehicles. Abdulraheem, Tongo, Orimadegun, and Akinbami (2016) further reiterated that lack of care by a medical personnel, infant ambu bag and supplemental oxygen during transport for better medical care accounted for poor neonatal outcomes among sick

neonates within the first 12 hours and first week of life.

All the primary and secondary health facilities that were included in this study lacked a mobile/cellular/land phone that was procured or maintained by the facility for the purpose of communication among healthcare providers when there is a need to call for help in an emergency care of neonates who require management for perinatal asphyxia. Similarly, there were no formal referral forms in all the facilities that were included in the study. This means that there was no effective or prior communication with the personnel at the tertiary facilities where the neonates would receive better medical care, thus causing a delay in management at the facilities to which the neonates have been referred (Abdulraheem et al., 2016).

5.5 Barriers to the Management of PA

5.5.1 In-service training and update

Findings from previous studies point that some of the ways by which providers' knowledge and ability to manage perinatal asphyxia can be effectively built include supportive supervision, and competency-based pre-service and in-service training (Kim et al., 2013). On the other hand, results from this study show that lack of facility sponsored in-service training and lack of supportive supervision strongly affects healthcare provider's ability to manage perinatal asphyxia. This is similar to the findings from a multi-country analysis study of the bottlenecks to basic newborn care and newborn resuscitation where Enweronu-laryea et al. (2015) described the quality of training (pre-service and in-service) and support supervision as inadequate.

Majority of the respondents reported that their facilities lacked skill stations where the management of PA can be frequently demonstrated and simulated. This

affected their ability to have regular hands on as well as keep their skills updated in the management of PA. When skill stations are present for simulation and demonstration, the cost of training will be reduced, the time that healthcare providers have to take off work to be able to attend trainings outside their health facility will be reduced and the frequency of practice will be increased thereby increasing the knowledge and improving the skills of healthcare providers in the management of PA.

5.5.2 Equipment and Supplies

Findings from a study conducted by Mzurikwao, Kapalat, and Ernest (2018) on the factors that influence the knowledge and practice of skilled birth attendants on helping babies breathe in Tanzania indicates that healthcare providers who did not have adequate equipment for newborn resuscitation were not able to manage babies with perinatal asphyxia adequately because of the intermittent nature in their practice of the procedure. Over two-third of the respondents further cited deficient supply and repair of resources as a barrier to the management of PA. Some of the resources that were usually lacking include equipment, supplies and medications for perinatal asphyxia management.

Majority of the participants expressed displeasure about incessant lack of supply of equipment and medications. When these resources are unavailable, healthcare providers are incapacitated to manage asphyxiated neonates effectively no matter their level of knowledge and competence. Some of the healthcare providers cited occasions where parents of asphyxiated babies have gone in search of medications

from pharmacies outside the hospital and were delayed or unable to get the drugs. Such delays have been documented in literature to portend a huge negative effect on the outcome of these neonates.

5.5.3 Frequency of Cases Managed

In this study, although more than one-third of the respondents have not managed a newborn with perinatal asphyxia, more than half felt somewhat confident because they seldom manage perinatal asphyxia while majority felt somewhat competent because of the need for an in-service training in the management of babies with perinatal asphyxia. Similarly, skill station for simulation was only observed in one health facility, whereas, more than half of the respondents submitted that there are no skill stations in the facilities where they work. This means that healthcare providers will not have the opportunity to practice and demonstrate the management of PA to improve and maintain their skill to offer this critical service.

5.6 Conclusion

Contrary to the hypothesized association between knowledge and pre-service training of healthcare providers, the results from this study signify that the knowledge of healthcare providers who had a recent training on newborn resuscitation have a good knowledge score when compared with others who do not have a recent training in newborn resuscitation. Kim et al. (2013) in a similar study also observed in their study that training was associated with greater knowledge among healthcare providers. Furthermore, this result is in tandem with findings from a previous study by Mzurikwao, Kapalat, and Ernest (2018) who as well posited that healthcare providers who have a previous training on neonatal resuscitation had

adequate knowledge while those who have never attended such trainings did not. These results therefore suggest that training and regular in-service training on newborn resuscitation and management of newborns with perinatal asphyxia will not only bridge the skill-knowledge divide but also maintain the knowledge of healthcare providers in the management of PA at a consistently high level.

5.7 Recommendations

- There is a need for regulatory bodies to put adequate measures in place to ensure that employers are regularly building the professional capacity of their staff.
- Sustainable and consistent sources of funding for equipment and supplies should be made available to substitute for the removal of out of pocket expenses that the government is advocating.
- Competency-based approach should be introduced to pre-service education and in-service training. Training programs ideally should incorporate monitoring and evaluation tools for assessing program cost-effectiveness and impact on health outcomes.
- Common PA assessment, monitoring and diagnostic indicators should be developed to provide a guide for proper diagnosis and management of PA by healthcare providers, both at global and facility levels.
- Skilled birth attendants should be employed and deployed to all health facilities in the State so that there will be at least one SBA to attend to deliveries at any point in time, especially at the primary health facility level.
- Strengthening of the capacities of healthcare providers in form of sponsored

in-service training; provision of adequate equipment, medications and other supplies; provision of simulation areas within the health facility; and current guidelines in delivery rooms for the management of PA should be made available across all facility levels.

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APPENDIX I

Objective 1: Prevalence

This will be assessed for the period of 3-months that this project will be carried out.

Cases managed	1 st mth	2 nd mth	3 rd mth	Total	
Newborns					
Total number of babies delivered					
Number of singleton					
Number of twins, triplets or more					
Number of newborns with birth weight below 2500grams					
Number with birth weight above 2500grams					
Number of female newborns					
Number of male newborns					
Number of live births					
Number of newborns whose APGAR score were recorded at birth					
Number of newborns with APGAR score					

of ≤ 6 in first minute of life					
Number of newborns with APGAR score of > 6 in first minute of life					
Number of newborns with APGAR score of ≤ 6 in first 5 minute of life					
Number with APGAR score of ≥ 6 in first 5 minute of life					
Number of fresh stillbirths					
Number of macerated stillbirths					
Number of newborns with asphyxia					
Number of newborns resuscitated					
Number of newborns that breathed spontaneously after stimulation					
Number of newborns that breathed spontaneously after 5mins of basic resuscitation					
Number of newborns that breathed spontaneously after 20mins of advanced resuscitation					
Number of babies that were referred for intensive newborn care					
Number of newborns that could not be resuscitated					

APPENDIX II:

Objective 2: Knowledge of Healthcare Providers on Newborn Resuscitation

SECTION A

(Please respond by ticking in the box next to the answer most suitable for you)

1. Age at last birthday:
2. Gender: Male () Female ()
3. Marital status: Single () Married () Divorced () Others ()
4. Religion: Christianity () Islam () Traditionalist () Others ()
5. Occupational category: Registered Nurse () Registered Midwife () Associate Degree Nurse () Generalist Medical Doctor () Pediatrician () CHEW () Anesthetic Nurse () Anesthetist () Pediatric Nurse () Others ()
6. What year did you complete the basic training for your occupational category?
7. Was newborn resuscitation part of your training in school? Yes () No ()
8. Ward or unit: Labour ward..... Maternity ward..... Newborn Theater.....
9. How long have you worked in this unit?.....
10. Have you received any in-service training or training updates on newborn resuscitation in this facility? Yes () No ()
11. If yes, please specify the training attended and year?.....
12. If no, what factor was responsible?
There was no fund () There was no time () Location of training is far ()

I am not aware of such training () It was not necessary ()

13. Is the management of PA part of your responsibilities in this facility?

13. Have you managed newborns with perinatal asphyxia in the past 3 months?

Yes () No ()

14. How will you describe your confidence in the management of newborns with perinatal asphyxia? Very confident () Somewhat confident (needs coaching/training)

() Not confident ()

15. How will you describe your competence in the management of newborns with perinatal asphyxia? Very competent () Somewhat competent (needs coaching/training) ()

Not competent ()

SECTION B

Instruction: The following includes a list of some instruments that may be used for the MANAGEMENT OF PA. From each of the columns labeled required, available and functioning, you are to tick 'yes' OR 'no' for each of the equipment based on your knowledge and not applicable if the procedure is not done in your unit.

	Required		Available		Functioning		Not Applicable
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Basic resuscitation equipment							
Infant ambu bag							
Stethoscope							
Newborn face mask sizes 0 and 1							

Bulb syringe/aspirator/mucus extractor							
Pre-warmed towels							
Newborn resuscitation table							
Clock with seconds							
Advanced Resuscitation Equipment							
Suction tube (6F, 8F and 10F)							
Mucus extractor/simple suction/bulb syringe							
Radiant warmer							
Newborn face mask sizes 0 and 1							
Suction machine							
Endotracheal tube							
Nasogastric tube							
Neonatal laryngoscope							
Mode of oxygen delivery (nasal catheter, nasal prongs, face mask)							
	Required		Available		Functioning		Not Applicable
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Oxygen tubing							
Oxygen cylinder							
Oxygen concentrator							
Resuscitaire							
Other supplies							

Electronic cardiac (ECG) monitor and monitor leads							
Pulse oximeter sensor							
Temperature sensor							
Carbon dioxide detector							
Measuring tape/endotracheal tube insertion depth table							
Meconium aspirator							
Flow meter							
Oxygen blender							
Scissors							
	Required		Available		Not Applicable		
Medications	Yes	No	Yes	No			
0.9% N/saline							
10% D/W							
8.4% Sodium bicarbonate							
1:10,000 (0.1mg/mL) epinephrine							
Adrenaline							
Whole blood							
Methylated spirit							
Syringes (1mL, 2mL, 5mL, and 10mL)							
Antiseptic lotion							
Water-proof tape or securing device							

Sterile gloves					
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SECTION C

Instruction: Under-listed are some items to test your knowledge on the MANAGEMENT OF PA. You are to choose 'yes' if you agree with any of the statements, or 'no' if you think the statement is wrong.

Preparation for the management of perinatal asphyxia	Yes	No
This often begins with proper monitoring of maternal and fetal conditions during labour		
Assessment of susceptibility of the newborn is included in the preparation		
Close monitoring of labour essentially hastens the onset of newborn resuscitation.		
The condition of the fetus will determine healthcare personnel that will make up the resuscitation team		
Cleaning and sterilizing all equipment is a way of getting ready for another resuscitation		
Make sure resuscitation equipment are complete and in a ready to use condition before each delivery		
Wash hands and wear gloves		
Know how to call for help and who is available		
Tell mother what is going on		
The following are some of the factors that predispose a baby to asphyxia:		

The gestational age		
Fetal distress		
Clarity of the amniotic fluid		
The sex of the expected baby		
Number of babies that are expected to be delivered		
The following signs should be present before a diagnosis of asphyxia is made:		
Bradypnoea (below 30 cycles/min)		
Heart rate below 100 beats per minute		
Central cyanosis (blue tongue)		
Apgar score less than 5 in first minute of life		
Baby not crying		
The following are the preliminary steps of asphyxia management:		
Delay cord clamping till 30 secs after delivering a baby with abnormality		
Turn baby upside down to improve blood circulation to vital organs		
Dry baby thoroughly with warm towel after birth and remove it thereafter		
Wrap or cover with a new warm towel		
Place newborn face up on flat but firm surface (resuscitation table)		
Suction routinely		
Suction ONLY if meconium or blood is present in oral/nasal secretions		

Suction mouth before nose		
Provide tactile stimulation		
	Yes	No
Explain to mother what is happening		
Golden minute after birth is 60 seconds after birth		
Golden minute after birth is 120 seconds after birth		
What do you do when resuscitating with bag and mask?		
Check for and remove obstruction from mouth and nose		
Suctioning should be done by a provider that is skilled in the procedure		
Suctioning should ONLY be done under good light		
Suction well if blood or meconium is in the newborn's mouth and/or nose		
If baby is still not breathing, start ventilating		
Position head in a slightly extended position		
Place mask to cover chin, mouth and nose		
Ensure complete seal between mask, mouth and nose		
Ventilate chest 1 or 2 times and see if chest is rising		
Do not waste time by checking for chest rising, continue ventilation		
Ventilate 40 times/min per minute		
Pause to determine if baby is breathing spontaneously		
If baby is breathing and there is no sign of respiratory difficulty:		

Suction for a few minutes more		
Initiate breastfeeding		
Keep baby warm beside mother		
Continue monitoring the baby		
After 20mins, if baby does NOT begin breathing, heart rate is less than 60bpm, or if there is intercostals retraction or grunting;		
Slap or flick baby's soles		
Aspirate the baby's stomach		
Holding baby's feet carefully, turn baby upside down and swing back and forth		
Intubate if not already done		
Continue chest compressions, maintain oxygenation and ventilation		
Squeeze the chest		
Administer oxygen if available		
Explain to mother what is happening		
Arrange for immediate transfer for special care		
If there is no gasping or breathing at all after 20 minutes of ventilation, stop ventilating		
Post resuscitation management		
Check vitals		
Ensure that there is normal perfusion		
Administer normal saline bolus if capillary refill time is prolonged		
Transfuse if there is evidence of blood loss		

Start IV 10% dextrose for the next 12 hours		
Check blood glucose every 12 hours in the first 72 hours of life		
Maintain blood glucose between 60 and 120mg/dl		
	Yes	No
Administer phenobarbitone if the baby has seizures		
Continue monitoring vitals and urine output		
Initiate intra gastric tube feeding until vitals become stable		
Shift to breastfeeding as soon as possible		
If no improvement or deterioration, REFER		
Post-procedure tasks		
Wash reusable catheters, mucus extractor, masks and masks in water and detergent		
Use a syringe to flush catheters and tubing		
Boil		
Keep in a clean dry place for later use		

APPENDIX III: FACILITY READINESS

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To be completed by the principal researcher or research assistant

Section A: Service Availability

	Nature of services available (Tick as appropriate)	Yes	No	Remarks
	Outpatient			
	Inpatient			
	Types of services available			
1	Obstetric			
2	Antenatal Care			
3	Cesarean Section			
4	Vaginal delivery			
5	Pediatric Outpatient			
6	Pediatric Inpatient			
7	Immediate newborn Care			
8	Neonatal Intensive Care			
9	Basic newborn resuscitation			
1 0	Advanced newborn resuscitation			

Section B: Personnel and Infrastructures

Facility code:.....
Unit:.....
Type of Facility (Tick as appropriate)
Primary health center () Comprehensive health center() State Hospital () Teaching

Hospital ()				
Setting (Tick as appropriate)				
Rural ()		Urban ()		
Personnel available				
Healthcare Professional	Yes	(Include	No (Remarks)	
	number)			
Specialist medical doctors				
Gynecologist				
Pediatrician				
Anesthetist				
Midwives				
Nursing Officers				
Medical Officers				
Community health workers				
Others (specify)				
Infrastructure	Yes	No	Remarks	
Communication				
Does this facility have a functioning cellular telephone or a private cellular phone that is available at all times and supported by the facility?				
Newborn care corner				

Does this facility have a newborn care corner with appropriate features?			
Ambulance/Transport For Emergencies Does this facility have a functioning ambulance or other vehicle for emergency that is stationed at this facility or operates from this facility?			
Does this facility have access to an ambulance or other vehicle for emergency transportation for clients that is stationed at another facility or that operates from another facility?			
Is fuel available in the vehicle today?			
Power supply			
During the past 7 days, was electricity (excluding any back-up generator) available at all times when the facility was open for services or interrupted for less than 2 hours at a time?			
Does this facility have any of the following other sources of electricity?			
Fuel operated generator			
Battery operated generator			
Solar system			
Others (Specify)			
Is the generator functional?			
Is there fuel or a charged battery today?			

Water supply			
Portable water available 24h/day and 7 days/week			
Processing of equipment for reuse			
Electric autoclave (pressure and wet heat)			
Non-electric autoclave			
Electric dry heat sterilizer			
Electric boiler or steamer (no pressure)			
Non-electric pot with cover for boiling/steam			
Heat source for non-electric equipment			

Section C: Equipment and Supplies

Basic resuscitation equipment	Available		Functioning		Not Applicable
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Infant ambu bag					
Stethoscope					
Newborn face mask sizes 0 and 1					

Bulb syringe/aspirator/mucus extractor					
Pre-warmed towels					
Radiant warmer					
Newborn resuscitation table					
Clock with seconds					
Resuscitation table					
Advanced Resuscitation Equipment					
Suction tube (6F, 8F and 10F)					
Mucus extractor/simple suction/bulb syringe					
Newborn face mask sizes 0 and 1					
Suction machine					
Endotracheal tube					
Nasogastric tube					
Neonatal laryngoscope					
Mode of oxygen delivery (nasal catheter, nasal prongs, face mask)					
Oxygen tubing					
	Available		Functioning		Not Applicable
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Oxygen cylinder					
Oxygen concentrator					

Resuscitaire					
Other supplies					
SpO2 monitor					
Electronic cardiac (ECG) monitor and monitor leads					
Pulse oximeter sensor					
Temperature sensor					
Carbon dioxide detector					
Measuring tape/endotracheal tube insertion depth table					
Meconium aspirator					
Flow meter					
Oxygen blender					
Scissors					
	Available		Expired		
Medications	Yes	No	Yes	No	
0.9% N/saline					
10% D/W					
8.4% Sodium bicarbonate					
1:10,000 (0.1mg/mL) epinephrine					
Adrenaline					
Phenobarbitone					

Whole blood				
Methylated spirit				
Syringes (1mL, 2mL, 5mL, and 10mL)				
Antiseptic lotion				
Water-proof tape or securing device				
Sterile gloves				

SECTION D

Clinical Protocol and Guidelines

Job Aids	Yes	No	Remarks
Are visual NR action plan guidelines present at the resuscitation area?			
Do the healthcare workers refer to the NR guidelines action plans during resuscitation?			
Are there flip charts for on job resuscitation training among healthcare providers in the labour unit?			

**Guidelines observed in service area:

APPENDIX IV

Under-listed are some of the factors that can influence a provider's ability to manage a newborn with perinatal asphyxia. Please, select the appropriate items in the options provided based on the availability of these factors in your facility and their effect on healthcare provider's ability to manage a newborn with perinatal asphyxia.

Factors	Available		If not available, can be a barrier	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Facility-related factors				
Infrastructure for perinatal asphyxia management				
Equipment supply or repair				
Replenishing out of stock supplies and medications				
Infrastructure technology				
Facility layout that supports newborn resuscitation				
Guideline/flowchart for management of PA in the delivery room				
Adequate human resources for newborn resuscitation				
Good Doctor-Nurse relationship				

Team approach during the MANAGEMENT OF PA				
Sponsored in-service training				
Sponsored refresher training				
Mentoring/modeling in newborn resuscitation				
Effective supervision and feedback				
Skill stations or simulations				
Perinatal mortality audits				
Staff performance evaluation				
Healthcare provider-related factors				
Pre-service training in the basic management of PA				
Skilled personnel				
Personnel confidence				
Good mentor-mentee relationship				
Long-term use of non-evidence based practice				
Resistance to change				
Effective communication during the procedure				
Documenting intervention				
Use of delivery registers				
Number of perinatal asphyxia that have been previously managed by the provider				

APPENDIX V

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW GUIDE

Good day. My name is ADURAMO, Esther T. I am a post-graduate student of the

Department Nursing Science, Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria. I am conducting a study on 'Facility readiness for newborn resuscitation for perinatal asphyxia in health facilities in Osun State'. I will like to appeal that you should be as open as possible as the information provided will not be used against you or anyone in this facility in any way. The information provided will only be assessed by the researcher and the project supervisor. I will be asking you some personal questions about yourself, and then about your perception about what constitute barriers to effective resuscitation as an intervention for asphyxia in newborn babies in your facility. You will be engaged in a face-to-face interview session in a place and a time that is convenient for you for a period of 10-15 minutes. Participation in this study is voluntary and you may choose to discontinue for reasons best known to you or if you feel uncomfortable at any point in time.

I want to appeal again that you should supply answers to the questions that I will be asking you based on your perception and to the best of your knowledge.

Do feel free to ask me any question that may bother you at any point during the interview.

Please, append your signature if you wish to participate in this study.

Signature: ----- Date of interview: -----

Participant's code: -----

SECTION A

Introduction of Participant

Participant's code: -----

Professional Job category: -----

Participant's designation: -----

SECTION B

What do you understand by the term perinatal asphyxia?

I want you to describe what you understand by newborn resuscitation?

Can you share your experience of the cases of asphyxiated newborns that you have had in this facility?

How do you manage these cases?

What is your perception of the practice of newborn resuscitation by healthcare providers in this facility, especially in relation to the health outcomes of asphyxiated newborns?

Please discuss some of the factors that influence the practice of healthcare providers in this facility in the provision of newborn resuscitation?

Can you please explain to me what gives you motivation for newborn resuscitation?

Based on your personal experience, what are the challenges encountered during newborn resuscitation for asphyxiated babies?

What are the major obstacles that impede effective newborn resuscitation?

What recommendations will you make regarding the inactions of healthcare providers and their challenges during newborn resuscitation?